

Effect of Performance Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in
Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

By

Samuel Olufemi AWOTIDEBE
(ART/2015/1436)

Being a Research Project Submitted to the Department of Business Management, Faculty of
Management Sciences, Federal University, Dutsin-Ma, in Partial Fulfilment of the
Requirements for the Award of Bachelor of Science (BSc.) Degree in Business Management.

October, 2018.

Dedication

I dedicate this work to God, the Almighty, the Giver of life, wisdom, knowledge and understanding. To Him alone be all glory, honour and adoration, now and forevermore (amen).

Declaration

I, the undersigned, Samuel Olufemi Awotidebe with matriculation number ART/2015/1436 hereby declare that the project is my own original work and that it has not been submitted, and will not be presented at any other University for a similar or any other award of degree.

.....

Signature & date

Certification

This is to certify that this Project has been examined and approved for the Award of Bachelor of Science (BSc.) in Business Management, Faculty of Management Sciences, Federal University, Dutsin-Ma.

.....

Supervisor

.....

Sign & date

.....

Head of the Department

.....

Sign & date

.....

External Examiner

.....

Sign & date

Acknowledgements

I sincerely appreciate the efforts of my parents, Pastor P.O. & Lady Evang. E.O. Awotidebe for being the drivers through whom I came to this world and for ensuring that I acquire a university degree and also, to my entire family for their support, encouragement and inspiration during my academic pursuit.

I acknowledge the insightful comments, suggestions and guidance of my supervisor, Mr. Olusegun Kazeem, which contributed to the quality and timely completion of this research work. Furthermore, I am indebted to Mr Olufemi Aina for his financial and moral supports.

My most sincere appreciation goes to the Head of Department, Business Management and all my lecturers as well as other non-teaching staff, who have groomed me academically to a better person I am now. I salute the academic and non-academic efforts of other lecturers and non-lecturers from other Departments, who have also contributed to the success I have recorded academically and otherwise.

I thank the staff and Management of all the Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma (*vis-à-vis* - not in a particular order - First Bank Limited, United Bank for Africa PLC and Unity Bank PLC) for their cooperation during the course of the gathering of relevant data for this study.

I thank the Management and congregants of Apostolic Faith Church, Katsina Branch, Kano Zone, Abuja District under the physical leadership of Rev. Eyo Edet and Mrs Kike Taiwo Edet for their moral and financial supports. My appreciation will be incomplete if I fail to specially recognise Messers Clement Olushola Mashika and Samson Obarafo.

Lastly, my regards go to my classmates in the Business Management class, especially, my co-supervisee, Abdul-Rahman Alimat-Sadia.

Thanks and God bless you all abundantly and reward you with Heaven (amen).

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
Dedication	ii
Declaration	iii
Certification	iv
Acknowledgements	v
Table of Contents	vi
Abstract	x
List of Figures	xi
List of Tables	xii
Chapter One: Introduction	1
1.1 Background to the Study	1
1.2 Statement of Research Problem	3
1.3 Objectives of the Study	5
1.4 Research Questions	5
1.5 Research Hypothesis	6
1.6 Scope of the Study	6
1.7 Significance of the Study	7
1.8 Definition of Technical Terms	7
Chapter Two: Literature Review	9
2.1 Introduction	9
2.2 Concept of Performance Incentives	9
2.2.1 Financial Performance Incentives	10
2.2.1.1 Base Pay	11
2.2.1.2 Profit Sharing	12

2.2.1.3 Gain Sharing	12
2.2.1.4 Benefits	13
2.2.1.5 Initiative Rewards	13
2.2.1.6 Special Rewards	13
2.2.2 Non-financial Performance Incentives	13
2.2.2.1 Feedback	14
2.2.2.2 Recognition	14
2.2.2.3 Participation	16
2.2.2.4 Better Work Environment	17
2.2.2.5 Career Development	18
2.2.2.6 Training	19
2.3 Concept of Employee Efficiency	19
2.3.1 Major Interpretations of the Term "Employee Efficiency"	21
2.3.1.1 Productivity-oriented Approach	21
2.3.1.2 Objectives-oriented Approach	22
2.3.1.3 Performance-oriented Approach	22
2.3.2 Measuring Employee Efficiency	22
2.3.3 Ways to Improve Employee Efficiency	23
2.3.4 Seven Traits of an Efficient Employee	32
2.4 Conceptual Framework	34
2.5 Review of Empirical Studies	35
2.5.1 Relationship between Financial Performance Incentives and Employee Efficiency	40
2.5.2 Relationship between Non-financial Performance Incentives and Employee Efficiency	40
2.6 Theoretical Review	40

2.6.1 The Expectancy Theory	40
2.6.2 The Equity Theory	45
Chapter Three: Research Methodology	48
3.1 Introduction	48
3.2 Research Design	48
3.3 Population of the Study	49
3.4 Sample Size and Sampling Technique	49
3.4.1 Sample Size	49
3.4.2 Sampling Technique	50
3.5 Sources & Method of Data Collection	51
3.6 Validity and Reliability of Data Collection Instrument	52
3.6.1 Validity	52
3.6.2 Reliability	52
3.7 Method of Data Analysis	53
3.8 Measurement of Variables	54
3.9 Summary of Chapter	54
Chapter Four: Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation	55
4.1 Introduction	55
4.2 Data Presentation	55
4.2.1 Respondents' Demographic Characteristics	55
4.2.2 Performance Incentives Adopted by Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State to Encourage Employees	58
4.2.3 Effects of Financial Performance Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State	63

4.2.4 Effects of Non-financial Performance Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State	65
4.3 Test of Hypotheses	68
4.3.1 Hypotheses One	68
4.3.2 Hypotheses Two	78
4.3.3 Hypotheses Three	83
4.4 Discussion of Research Findings	89
Chapter Five: Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations	92
5.1 Summary of Findings	92
5.2 Conclusion	94
5.3 Recommendations	95
5.4 Limitations of the Study	95
5.5 Contributions to Knowledge	96
5.6 Suggestion for Further Studies	96
References	97
Appendix	103

Abstract

The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area (LGA) of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria. The population of the study comprised the sixty (60) employees of all the DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State, Nigeria (vis-à-vis First Bank Nigeria Ltd., United Bank for Africa PLC and Unity Bank PLC), of which a sample of 52 respondents was drawn using the proportional stratum allocation technique and the simple random sampling technique. The primary data was collected through the use of a structured questionnaire and was analysed through descriptive and inferential statistics using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The study, thus, found that DMBs in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State encourage employees through performance incentives and there are positive significant differences among the performance incentives used (vis-à-vis training, better working environment, benefits, base pay, feedback, recognition, participation, career development, profit sharing, gain sharing, initiative rewards and special rewards); financial performance incentives have a positive significant effect on employee efficiency in DMBs in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State and non-financial performance incentives have a positive significant effect on employee efficiency in DMBs in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. Hence, the study concluded that there is a positive significant effect of performance incentives on employee efficiency in DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria. The study, therefore, recommends that Management should increase the level of performance incentives they give their employees or as enjoyed by their employees in order to increase and sustain their employees' levels of efficiency. Management should continue to give their employees financial incentives and continue to allow their employees enjoy non-financial incentives in order to increase and sustain their efficiency, make them be willing to increase the speed at which they work, and for them to continue to do their work with no errors.

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1	Performance Incentives Constructs	10
Figure 2.2	Conceptual Framework	34
Figure 2.3	Simplified Expectancy Model	44
Figure 2.4	Equity in Compensation	45

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3.1	Study Population Distribution	49
Table 3.2	Sample Size Distribution	51
Table 4.1	Frequency Distribution of the Respondents' Demographic Characteristics	55
Table 4.2	Performance Incentives Adopted by Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State to Encourage Employees	59
Table 4.3	Effects of Financial Performance Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State	63
Table 4.4	Effects of Non-financial Performance Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State	66
Table 4.5	Chi-Squared (X^2) Test Showing the Result of Hypothesis One	69
Table 4.6	Computation of Chi-square Test Statistic for Hypothesis One	74
Table 4.7	Chi-Squared (X^2) Test Showing the Result of Hypothesis Two	78
Table 4.8	Computation of Chi-square Test Statistic for Hypothesis Two	81
Table 4.9	Chi-Squared (X^2) Test Showing the Result of Hypothesis Three	83
Table 4.10	Computation of Chi-square Test Statistic for Hypothesis Three	87

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Employees are forced to spend more time at the office – certainly exceeding the typical 40-hour work per week; but, exceeding the office hours does not mean increasing their efficiency. Instead, firms should make an effort to increase the efficiency of the employees, which will lead to individual growth and development of the firm (Makad, 2015). Many companies' returns are under pressure; hence, it is important that employees carry out the correct tasks in the right way. By working efficiently, more can be produced with the same amount of input (resources), thereby, achieving more for lower costs, a higher return and less pressure (Noordzij, 2013). According to Drucker (1974), efficiency means “doing things in the right way”. Furthermore, employee efficiency is an employee characteristic, which relates to the speed and accuracy of an employee at the job task. The concept relates to employee productivity, which provides that the more efficient an employee is, the more productive they will be if well-managed (Fandom, 2017). Invariably, employee efficiency is a complex measurable parameter which characterizes an output produced by efforts and achievements of an employee (TaskManagementGuide, 2018). Akerele (1991) blamed the productivity of Nigerian workers on several factors; among them is employer’s failure to provide adequate compensation for hard work and the indiscipline of the privileged class that arrogantly displays their wealth, which is very demoralizing to working class and consequently reduced their productivity.

Business organizations are facing significant challenges on internal and external work environment, so, organizations cannot maintain institutional performance without providing incentives to their employees based on their efficient and effective work. Incentives are variable

awards granted to employees according to variations in their performance as anything that can attract an employee's attention and motivate them to work can be called incentive. An incentive aims at improving the overall performance of an organization (Malhotra, 2017). Incentives are financial rewards paid to workers whose production exceeds a predetermined standard. It was Fredrick Taylor who popularized scientific management and the use of financial incentives, such as systematic soldiering and fair day's work, in the late 1800s (Dessler, 2008). Flippo (1984) defines performance incentives as the payment made to workers or group of workers based on the amount of output or result achieved or payment made for the purpose of motivating workers' performance towards a particular high target. Typically, different types of incentives are categorized into two groups: financial and non-financial incentives. While financial incentives include base pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits, initiative rewards and special rewards (Huttu, 2010), non-financial incentives comprise feedback to employees (Bari, Arif & Shaib, 2013; Huttu, 2010), recognition (Bari, Arif & Shaib, 2013; Huttu, 2010; Oburu & Atambo, 2016; Sammer, 2011), possibilities to participation (Huttu, 2010; Oburu & Atambo, 2016), better work environment (Bari, Arif & Shaib, 2013; Oburu & Atambo, 2016) career development (Bari, Arif & Shaib, 2013; Oburu & Atambo, 2016; Sammer, 2011) and training (Oburu & Atambo, 2016; Sammer, 2011; Waqas & Saleem, 2014).

Unfortunately, some of the employees of the deposit money banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State are not efficient in their work. For instance, some of the customers of one of the banks once complained that the bank employees were too slow when posting deposits, while another bank did not have an effective and efficient customer care representatives. While attending to customers, some employees of another bank within the study area would just leave the counter without properly excusing themselves from the customers.

Against this background, this study is an attempt to contribute to the body of knowledge on the subject matter by conducting a study on the effect of performance incentives on employee efficiency using Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State.

1.2 Statement of Research Problem

Several Studies on incentives and employee performance, incentives and employee attitude, incentives and organizational performance have been conducted. For instance, Al-Aydi (2000) conducted a study to investigate the effect of incentives on the level of performance in the textile industry in Iraq and the study found that there is a weak relationship between incentives system and level of performance and between wages system and level of performance. However, Al-Harhi (1999) examined how financial and moral incentives can be used to raise efficiency of employees in the Department of Civil Defence in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia and the study found that financial and moral incentives are unsatisfactory and may lead to a decrease in the level of performance of employees. But, when Al-Nsour (2012) investigated the relationship between incentives and organizational performance for employees in the Jordanian Universities, the study found that there is significant positive relationship between financial & moral incentives and organizational performance in the Jordanian Universities. Bari, Arif and Shaib (2013) also conducted a study to find out the impact of non-financial rewards on employee attitude and factors which affect employee performance at workplace in the business institutes of Karachi and the results showed that non-financial rewards positively impacts employee attitude and performance in the workplace. On the other hand, Huttu (2010), through critical literature review and interview research, studied how different incentives affect performance and job satisfaction and the study found that there are two different aspects in rewarding, which are effectiveness and humanity. The rewarding of the humanity-aspect is more important in generating job satisfaction

whereas the rewarding of the effectiveness-*aspect* affects performance and that different incentives have different effects on performance and job satisfaction like it was posited. Oburu and Atambo (2016) studied the effect of non-financial compensation on employee performance of micro finance institutions in Kenya with special reference to Wakenya Pamoja Sacco in Kisii County, Kenya and the study found that indeed non-financial incentives contribute to better employee performance in the Micro Finance Industry in Kenya, and the industry has benefited from non-financial compensation. Furthermore, Shah, Higgins and Friedman (1998) conducted a study on performance incentives and means: how regulatory focus influences goal attainment and found that motivation and performance are greater when the regulatory focus of task incentives and means match (vs. mismatch) the chronic regulatory focus of the performers. However, when Okwudili (2015) examined the effect of non-monetary rewards on productivity of employees among selected government parastatals in Abia State, Southeast-Nigeria, the study found that there is a negative significant relationship between type of non-monetary reward received and employees' productivity, but, non-monetary rewards and productivity of employees have a positive relationship. In their study on differential effects of incentive motivators on work performance, Stajkovic and Luthans (2001) conducted an empirical study on differential effects of incentive motivators on work performance in two facilities which conducted the same tasks and located several miles apart from each other and found that monetary incentives improved performance by over thirty per cent compared with those who did not get incentives. Rajendran, Mosisa and Nedelea (2017) investigated effects of non-monetary benefits on employees' performance on Bako Agriculture Research Center and found that there is a relationship between non-monetary benefits and employees work performance.

Unfortunately, there is no known study that has been conducted on the effects of performance incentives on employee efficiency. Hence, until now, there is still a research gap with regard to the effect of performance incentives on employee efficiency. Consequently, the study sought to fill the gap and provide a well-organized investigation into the effect of performance incentives (especially, the performance incentives associated with financial and non-financial incentives) on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study was to determine the effect of performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria. In line with the broad objective, the specific objectives were to:

1. Examine whether Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area encourage employees through performance incentives.
2. Determine the effect of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area.
3. Evaluate the effect of non-financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area.

1.4 Research Questions

In pursuit of the research objectives of the study, the research addressed the following research questions:

1. What are the performance incentives used in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area to encourage employees?

2. What are the effects of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area?
3. What are the effects of non-financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

To achieve the objectives stated above, the study tested the following hypotheses:

- H₀1: There are no significant differences among performance incentives used to encourage employees in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area.
- H₀2: There are no significant effects of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area.
- H₀3: There are no significant effects of non-financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study focused on effect of performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area. The independent variable is performance incentives, which was measured by financial incentives (base pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits, initiative rewards and special rewards) and non-financial incentives (feedback to employees, recognition, participation, better work environment, career development and training) while the dependent variable is employee efficiency, which was measured by accuracy. The units of analysis were the junior and senior staffs of Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no known study on effects of performance incentives on employee efficiency had been conducted in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State.

1.7. Significance of the Study

The study served as important information to Managers of Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State in ascertaining what aspect of performance incentives or what combination of performance incentives should be used to improve the efficiency of their employees and to know if the performance incentives they adopted to encourage employees in their branches really have any significant effect (whether positive or negative) on the efficiency of the employees. Furthermore, the study helped the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Nigerian Government to know what policies to formulate, which employees in the banking sectors would benefit from. Finally, the study contributed to existing literature on performance incentives (financial and non-financial) as regards the effect of performance incentives are to be used to improve employee efficiency, which would be of immense benefit to future researchers.

1.8 Definition of Technical Terms

1.8.1 Incentives

Incentives are variable awards granted to employees according to variations in their performance. Anything that can attract an employee's attention and motivate them to work can be referred to as incentive.

1.8.2 Performance Incentives

Performance incentives are the payment made to workers or group of workers based on the amount of output or result achieved or payment made for the purpose of motivating workers' performance toward a particular high target.

1.8.3 Efficiency

Efficiency means doing things in the right way. It is the ability to act or produce effectively with a minimum waste, expenditure or unnecessary effort. Efficiency is measured by quality.

1.8.4 Employee Efficiency

Employee efficiency is an employee characteristic, which relates to the speed and accuracy of an employee at the job task.

1.8.5 Accuracy

Accuracy refers to correctness or the ability to avoid errors. In other words, it is the correctness or truthfulness of something or the ability to be precise and avoid errors.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter focused on conceptual issues, empirical studies and theoretical reviews. To address the subject matter of the study, efforts were directed towards a thorough review of literature on performance incentives and employee efficiency in order to have a better understanding of the concepts. The review of literature also aimed at providing a detailed account of previous empirical studies for the purpose of identifying what has been done and what is left to be done in order to contribute to the body of knowledge regarding the subject matter.

Hence, this chapter looked at performance incentives, financial performance incentives, non-financial performance incentives and employee efficiency, conceptual framework, review of empirical studies and theoretical reviews.

2.2 Concept of Performance Incentives

Flippo (1984) defined performance incentives as the payment made to workers or group of workers based on the amount of output or result achieved or payment made for the purpose of motivating workers' performance towards a particular high target. Performance incentives are a combination of both financial and non-financial incentives. Typically, different types of incentives are categorized into two groups: financial and non-financial incentives. While financial incentives include base pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits, initiative rewards and special rewards (Huttu, 2010), non-financial incentives comprise feedback to employees (Bari, Arif & Shaib, 2013; Huttu, 2010), recognition (Bari, Arif & Shaib, 2013; Huttu, 2010; Oburu & Atambo, 2016; Sammer, 2011), employee participation (Huttu, 2010; Oburu & Atambo, 2016), better work environment (Bari, Arif & Shaib, 2013; Oburu & Atambo, 2016) career development

(Bari, Arif & Shaib, 2013; Oburu & Atambo, 2016; Sammer, 2011) and training (Oburu & Atambo, 2016; Sammer, 2011; Waqas & Saleem, 2014).

Figure 2.1 Performance Incentives Constructs
(Source: Self-made, 2018)

2.2.1 Financial Performance Incentives

There is nothing new about using incentives to motivate workers. Fredrick Taylor popularized the use of financial incentives – financial rewards paid to workers whose production exceeds some predetermined standard – in the late 1800s. As a supervisory employee of the Midvale Steel Company, Taylor had become concerned with what he called "systematic soldiering", which is the tendency of employees to work at the slowest pace possible and to produce at the minimum acceptable level (Dessler, 2005). Financial incentives aim to raise production efficiency and improve performance through encouraging individual to behave in a desired way. Financial incentives are the most important and influential factors to the individual's desire to work when such wages are appropriate and capable of satisfying his needs. On the contrary, low

payment that is not appropriate to his efforts of work leads to the low efficiency or productivity (Al-Harthi, 1999). Financial incentives alone are not sufficient unless assisted by other types of incentives. Their effects are limited to satisfy the biological needs of individuals and have a little impact after it reaches the limit of needs. Therefore, individuals who are not seeking to increase production for additional financial gains, thus, cannot be financially motivated to contribute in increasing production except for a certain amount based on their efforts (Aldubekhi, 1991). Lotta (as cited in Okwudili, 2015) agreed that financial incentives are indeed effective in motivating employees. Ojokuku and Sajuyigbe (as cited in Okwudili, 2015) have also found that financial incentives (pay satisfactions dimensions) have significant effect on employee's performance. However, Perry, Mesch, and Paarlberg (2006) discovered that financial reward is not the most motivating factor, and financial incentives have a de-motivating effect among employees (Srivastava, 2001). Several studies have found that among employees surveyed, money was not the most important motivator, and in some instances managers have found money to have a de-motivating or negative effect on employees' performance (Oburu & Atambo, 2016). Hence, in order to increase employee efficiency, Dzuaranin (2012) suggested that companies that only use financial incentives must also introduce non-financial incentives to their performance incentive systems. Financial incentives include base pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits, initiative rewards and special rewards. Except for benefits and special rewards, financial incentives are typically paid as money. However benefits and special rewards are part of financial incentives because recipients benefit from them economically (Huttu, 2010).

2.2.1.1 Base Pay

According to Stajkovic and Luthans (2001), a base pay is the pay employee typically gets from the job. It is a task specific minimum pay. A base pay does not play a very important role when

talking about motivating employees because all employees working in the same task get the same base pay regardless of performance. It is, however, important to notice that base pay is more important as a motivator at a lower organizational level than upper level because at lower level a base pay is smaller and it is important in fulfilling one's physiological needs.

2.2.1.2 Profit Sharing

Elinkeinoelämän keskusliitto (as cited in Hutu, 2010) argued that profit sharing means that employees are paid a proportion of the organization's pre-tax profits. According to definition, we can talk about profit sharing compensation when the interdependence between profit sharing and organization's profit is over 50 per cent. This means that organization can pay profit sharing compensation based on only organization's profit or based on organization's profit and some other measures, for example, customer satisfaction. However, organization's profit has to be in the biggest role in determining whether profit sharing compensation is paid for organization's employees or not (Huttu, 2010).

2.2.1.3 Gain Sharing

Gain sharing determinants for compensation can include different goals or their combinations such as economic key ratios, customer satisfaction and some specific development targets. Also, organization's profit can be one of the determinants for gain sharing; but, profit's proportion of total determinant has to be less than 50 per cent (Elinkeinoelämän keskusliitto 2005, as cited in Huttu, 2010). According to Hanlon and Taylor (as cited in Huttu, 2010) gain sharing creates a stronger link between pay and performance than profit sharing because bonus payments in gain sharing systems are based on specific criteria of documented improvements within specific group.

2.2.1.4 Benefits

Tremblay, Sire and Pelchat (as cited in Huttu, 2010) posit that benefits can be in form of company car, company flat, life insurance, private medical care and annual holiday entitlement. Also, flexible working hours and exercise possibilities are examples of different benefits. Nowadays, emphasis is being placed on flexible benefits. In flexible or cafeteria benefit systems, employer offers different kinds of benefits and employees can choose their own benefits packages among benefits that had been offered by the employer (Huttu, 2010).

2.2.1.5 Initiative Rewards

However, according to Jeffrey and Shaffer (as cited in Huttu, 2010), initiative rewards refer to rewards given to employees for their useful initiatives. The main goal of initiative rewards is to encourage employees to develop work and their working place.

2.2.1.6 Special Rewards

Special rewards are non-monetary tangible rewards, which can be almost everything. For example: trips, tickets to sport event or golf club membership offered by employer can be special rewards. Special rewards can be delivered unexpected without any bonus plan or there can be bonus plan according to which rewards are distributed (Jeffrey & Shaffer 2007, as cited in Huttu, 2010).

2.2.2 *Non-financial Performance Incentives*

Non-financial (performance) incentives include feedback to employees (Bari, Arif & Shaib, 2013; Huttu, 2010), recognition (Bari, Arif & Shaib, 2013; Huttu, 2010; Oburu & Atambo, 2016; Sammer, 2011), employee participation (Huttu, 2010; Oburu & Atambo, 2016), better work environment (Bari, Arif & Shaib, 2013; Oburu & Atambo, 2016) career development (Bari, Arif

& Shaib, 2013; Oburu & Atambo, 2016; Sammer, 2011) and training (Oburu & Atambo, 2016; Sammer, 2011; Waqas & Saleem, 2014).

Furthermore, Okwudili (2015) explained that non-financial incentives are non-financial rewards, which are non-monetary/non-cash such as social recognition, praise and genuine appreciation. Moreover, Oburu and Atambo (2016) have added that social recognition includes: certificate, acknowledgement and genuine appreciation. However, Nelson and Quick (2003) argued that praise and recognition are the most efficient intrinsic reward that enhance employee performance.

2.2.2.1 Feedback

Feedback has been defined as actions taken by an external agent in order to provide information regarding some aspects of one's task performance (Kluger & DeNisi, 1996). Feedback is an efficient and quick way to motivate employees because feedback is given in the working situation (Stajkovic & Luthans, 2001). One of the advantages of feedback is that besides the fact that it motivates, it also provides important knowledge of employee's performance for the employee himself (Huttu, 2010). Kluger and DeNisi (1996) found that feedback has also, an indirect effect on motivation. Feedback gives important information to employee on how he or she is performing, which in turn helps employee to set goals and attain goals that are set earlier.

2.2.2.2 Recognition

Recognition is defined as personal attention which expresses interest, approval and appreciation (Stajkovic & Luthans, 2001). According to Narveed (as cited in Oburu & Atambo, 2016), recognition and rewards have a direct impact on motivation of the employees and increase their efficiency. Recognition is a non-financial compensation (Kurfi, 2013). Recognition refers to the general acknowledgement or confirmation of a given occurrence or performance (Petresca &

Simon, 2008). According to Harrison (as cited in Oburu & Atambo, 2016), employee recognition is seen as a timely, informed or formal acknowledgement of an individual's behaviour and effort that directly supports the achievement of organizational goals and values usually beyond normal expectation levels. It is, therefore, an employer's acknowledgement of an employee's accomplishment and effort towards the organization's goals. It connotes the act of giving special attention to employee's actions, efforts, behaviour or performance, which can either be physically or psychologically or both. It is actually one way of dealing with the employees' feelings. According to Nolan (as cited in Oburu & Atambo, 2016), employee recognition is one of the ways of motivating staff in an organization, making them feel valued and improving the overall attraction and employee retention. Not all employees are motivated to perform beyond the essential minimum with monetary incentives alone. It is therefore incumbent on organizations to provide relevant awards on merit as a form of employee recognition (Oburu & Atambo, 2016). Taylor (2017) explained that according to a research published in the *European Journal of Business and Management*, empowerment and recognition of employees can motivate employees to perform better, accomplish more, and ensure the better performance of the organization. Some organizations use recognition to spur individual performance while others use it to enhance overall organizational performance (Oburu & Atambo, 2016). Recognition can, for example, be verbal confession from the work that has been done well or the employee of the month prize (Huttu, 2010). According to Nolan (as cited in Oburu & Atambo, 2016), organizations can offer employee recognition in various ways ranging from the provisions of gifts cards, certificates, shopping vouchers, 'thank you', praise dinners, trophies, career advancement opportunities, trainings, appreciating ideas and respect where it deserves. Like participation, recognition is also a source of intrinsic motivation (Deci, et al., 1996; Herzberg,

1968; Maslow, 1947). Furthermore, social recognition is usually delivered verbally and it requires interpersonal skills of managers (Stajkovic & Luthans, 2001). Organizations have even devised recognition programmes such as “employee of the month/year schemes”, “long service awards”, etc. However, various studies have proved that it is a common occurrence in most organizations in failing to include recognition as a component of compensation (Ndeti, Ongecha, Mutiso, Kuria, Khasakhala, & Kokonya, 2007). Recognition is, however, the least expensive (Corby, White, & Stanworth, 2005) and yet it brings about more benefits from employees (Oburu & Atambo, 2016).

Although, there have not been many other studies about the effects of recognition on performance, but, considering motivation theories, four of them support the motivating effect of recognition. Both Maslow and Herzberg see recognition as a motivation factor. For instance, in Maslow’s hierarchy of needs, recognition satisfies individual’s need for esteem; but, according to self-efficacy theory, individual’s belief about his/her ability to perform the task is an important determinant of effort. Recognition can improve self-esteem which in turn can lead to higher effort and increase performance. Cognitive evaluation theory emphasizes the importance of need for competence as a source of intrinsic motivation. It is logical that recognition can fulfil the individual’s need for competence and increase motivation (Huttu, 2010).

2.2.2.3 Participation

Participation means that employees are able to take part and influence organization’s operations and contents of their own work (Brown, 1996; Fernie & Metcalf, 1995). For example, employees’ possibilities to choose working order or their own working times are examples of participation (Huttu, 2010). Employees’ possibility to participation is the source of intrinsic motivation (Herzberg, 1968; Fernie & Metcalf, 1995; Brown, 1996; Oburu & Atambo, 2016).

According to Brown (1996), participation is a key to activate employees' motivation. Participation engages employee in work and makes work more meaningful which in turn increases intrinsic motivation. Motivation theories such as Maslow's hierarchy of needs, Herzberg's motivation-hygiene theory and cognitive evaluation theory support participation's positive effect on performance. For instance, according to Maslow's hierarchy of needs, participation can fulfil peoples' social and self-actualization needs. Furthermore, in Herzberg's motivation-hygiene theory, participation is a motivating factor which increases motivation and job satisfaction. Cognitive evaluation theory hypothesizes that individual's basic needs are autonomy and competence. Moreover, participation gives employees the possibility to have influence on their work. In that way, participation can fulfil individual's need for autonomy, and motivate employees (Huttu, 2010). However, Oburu and Atambo (2016) contended that although participation has been considered the source of intrinsic motivation and some of the motivation theories support participation's motivating effect, various studies have found that generally, participation has modest positive effect on performance.

2.2.2.4 Better Work Environment

Employee efficiency increases as a result of a better workplace environment because it boosts the employee motivation and eventually improves their efficiency. Furthermore, a work environment where employees feel that they have reasons for doing work and get pleasure from doing their job motivates the employee. However, in working conditions where employees are not provided with adequate resources, tools, training, software and supplies, lead to the motivation and lesser productivity. The inefficient working conditions which include comfort issues like poor ventilation, seating, lightning and noise can cause anxiety and decrease the output (Hughes, 2007). The workplace with lack of privacy and communication barriers reduces motivation and

efficiency. A healthy workplace which is made by using ergonomic furniture and accessories, lightning and functional design will diminish distress and improve efficiency. Lack of praise, recognition and promotions in the workplace environment affect the motivation of employees. The presence of troublesome and negative employees also influences the employee's relationship with rest of colleagues in a negative way. As a result, the absenteeism rate increases and they are less likely to continue the job (Roelofsen, 2002). Relationship with the co-worker, equal opportunities for promotions, responsibility and autonomy are also components of working environment which can affect employee efficiency. Management should improve working conditions in order to improve efficiency and motivate the employees. Since employees are not robots so the workplace should have a gym and lounge for the wellbeing of employees (Oburu & Atambo, 2016).

2.2.2.5 Career Development

The lack of career development opportunities affects motivation and performance. If employees are offered opportunities for developing their careers by adapting skills, technologies and competencies essential for performance improvement and promotion, they will feel valued and motivated. Motivation is goal-oriented behaviour (Oburu & Atambo, 2016). According to this concept, employees can be motivated if their expectations concerning the goal accomplishment are linked with the specific actions on the part of management. Hence, employee efficiency will increase because they have a constant reminder that their actions will not only make them accomplish their goals, but, will also result in greater chances for their promotions. The provision of opportunities for learning and growth of the organizations can motivate the employee (Armstrong, 2001). Organizations pay more attention on developing their employees and enhancing their motivational aspects like self-esteem and self-actualization. So, they can

reach the most favourable performance. Equal opportunities for career advancement and equitable payment system and training can increase employee efficiency via motivation (Oburu & Atambo, 2016)

2.2.2.6 Training

The anticipation of future financial benefits, promotions and recognition motivates the employee to adapt new skills and technology at the training program. A training program that starts with a needs assessment and then inconsistency between actual and standard performance of trainee is analyzed. Later on, training objectives are made. After determining who wants the training and what sort of training should be given, the training program is implemented. The last step of the process is to evaluate the effectiveness of training programs (Oburu & Atambo, 2016). The lack of training will result in ignorance of the manager about the skills, competencies and knowledge that are decisive for the performance improvement and motivation. Organizations conduct training programs due to dynamic changes in the business environment which increases the efficiency of employees, as a result, the employees are promoted due to the training provided to them (Roscoe, 2002). Firms who spend more on training of the employee are more developed as the human resource training enhances the efficiency of the employee more than other resources (Khattak, Bashir, & Qureshi, 2010). Furthermore, employees are motivated to be trained because they foresee an increase in their confidence level, self-esteem and career satisfaction. The training and development brings more future opportunities for promotion. An involvement of employees in the training program and determining their training needs gives them ownership of the training process and adds to their efficiency (Murphy, Cross, & McGuire, 2006).

2.3 Concept of Employee Efficiency

Efficiency is very important in the activities of employees. Not only must firms do the right thing such as offering high-quality products, but, they must also produce their products efficiently (Everard & Burrow, 2001). According to Schermerhorn et al. (2017), Drucker has distinguished effectiveness from efficiency through his memorable quote: “There is surely nothing so useless as doing with great efficiency what should not be done at all”. Something is only efficient when it is effective. In other words, something is efficient if it has a useful effect. It has to be functional (Noordzij, 2013). Hence, one can only talk about efficiency when effectiveness is already in place. Efficiency is the ability to act or produce effectively with a minimum of waste, expenditure or unnecessary effort. The focus is on the resources and speed with which organisational goals are achieved. Drucker (1974) asserted that efficiency means 'doing things in the right way'. Efficiency is measured by output, which is the quantity produced over a given time (Everard & Burrow, 2001).

Employee efficiency is an employee characteristic, which relates to the speed and accuracy of an employee at the job task. The concept relates to employee productivity, which provides that the more efficient an employee is, the more productive they will be if well-managed (Fandom, 2017). Invariably, employee efficiency is a complex measurable parameter which characterizes an output produced by efforts and by achievements of an employee (TaskManagementGuide, 2018). Akerele (1991) has blamed the productivity of Nigerian workers on a number of factors among which are the failure of employers to provide adequate compensation for employees based on their diligence, and the indiscipline of the privileged class that arrogantly displays their wealth, which is very demoralizing to the working class to such an extent that it reduces their productivity. Love (1991) opined that how successfully resources are assigned in order to

achieve organizational goals in the right way determines the efficiency of such an organization. In other words, how well an organization converts inputs into outputs such as products, programmes and services speaks a lot about how efficient such an organization is. As a result of this, efficiency contributes to the success of an organization. According to Ghemawat and Ricart (1993), two categories of efficiency are often referred to, and they are: static efficiency and dynamic efficiency. Static efficiency relates to refining existing products, processes or opportunities; making improvements within existing conditions. Dynamic efficiency refers to the continuous development of new products, processes or opportunities so that profitability can improve. In most cases, the employee efficiency answers these questions:

- Is this employee useful to organization? (i.e. Does he produce more value than he consume?)
- How useful is this employee? (i.e. What is the worth of what he produces exactly?)

2.3.1 Major Interpretations of the Term "Employee Efficiency"

There is no single understanding of this quite wide term, but usually, sense of employee efficiency refers to the following conceptions, which intersect with each other in certain aspects and usually are used in a mixture (TaskManagementGuide, 2018):

2.3.1.1 Productivity-oriented Approach

It stands for objective appraising of the value produced by efforts and talents of the employee and comparing this value against the worth of inputs and resources provided to this employee by the organization. In other words, this attitude means determining the level of employee profitability: his or her ability to convert investments into direct profits or some long-term benefits.

2.3.1.2 Objectives-oriented Approach

It stands for determining an ability of employee to accomplish certain amount of work (or to achieve some other required objectives) within a given period of time or/and other business resources. This attitude identifies an employee as efficient one if he or she properly fulfills certain working plans or matches certain productive norms. These plans usually imply certain inbuilt level of profitability.

2.3.1.3 Performance-oriented Approach

This attitude means giving an appraisal to a manner, which an employee adheres to while carrying out his or her job. In this case, the employee efficiency is analyzed by measuring compliance of his/her activities with certain standards or requirements. This attitude states that employee is 100% efficient when he or she strictly follows a predefined procedure or workflow which is considered as efficient.

2.3.2 Measuring Employee Efficiency

While productivity measures quantity, efficiency measures quality. You could calculate a very high productivity number per employee, but that number alone does not give you any insight into the quality of work (in theory, an employee could seem very productive, but actually be producing horrible outputs). To compare the productivity numbers against a benchmark, you can compare the current productivity with the standard amount of effort needed for the same output. Divide the standard labour hours by the actual amount of time worked and multiply by 100. The closer the final number is to 100, the more effective your employees are. For example, let us say the standard labour hours for a certain project is 80 and the actual amount of time worked is 92. You would divide 80 by 92, and multiply by 100, calculating your efficiency to be 87%. In other words, if a company's standard labour hours for a

certain project is 80hrs and the actual amount of time worked is 92hrs, hence, efficiency = $\left(\frac{80}{92}\right) \times 100 = 87\%$ (Eposito, 2015).

Formula:
$$\left(\frac{\text{Standard Labour Hours}}{\text{Amount of Time Worked}} \right) \times 100 = \text{Efficiency}$$

According to Eposito (2015), in comparing productivity and efficiency, there are a few different ratios to consider, such as:

- i. Idle Time Ratio: $(\text{Production downtime} / \text{total labour hours}) \times 100$
- ii. Activity Ratio: $(\text{Expected hours needed to produce actual output} / \text{actual hours needed to complete}) \times 100$
- iii. Labour Capacity: $(\text{Actual hours worked} / \text{total budgeted labour hours}) \times 100$

2.3.3 Ways to Improve Employee Efficiency

Employees are considered to be the asset of an organization, and the level of the employees' efficiency in any organization is largely responsible for such an organization's profit-making ability and its long-run survival. Hence, it is not only important to recruit the right people, but it is also crucial to maintain their efficiency and productivity. These days, employees are forced to spend more time at the office, but, exceeding the office hours does not mean increasing the productivity. Instead, firms should make an effort to increase the efficiency of the workers which will lead to individual growth as well as the development of the firm (Makad, 2015). According to Hicks (2017), leaders and managers can improve employee efficiency while still saving time. Following are the fifteen various ways to increase employee efficiency at the office (Hicks, 2017; Makad, 2015; Taylor, 2017):

Delegation

Although, delegation seems the most obvious, but, it is often the most difficult to put into practice. Many a business owner considers their company as their baby; hence, they want to have a direct hand in everything that goes on with it. While there is nothing wrong with prioritizing quality (it is what makes a business successful, after all), the business owner checking over every small detail rather than delegating can waste everyone's valuable time. Instead, responsibilities should be given to qualified employees having the trust that they will perform the tasks well. This gives the employees the opportunity to gain skills and leadership experience that will ultimately benefit the company. They have been hired for a reason and they should be given a chance to prove the employer right.

Task-Skill Matching

Knowing one's employees' skills and behavioural styles is essential for maximizing efficiency. For example, an extroverted, creative, out-of-the-box thinker is probably a great person to pitch ideas to clients. However, they might struggle if they are given a more rule-intensive, detail-oriented task. Asking the employees to be great at everything they do is just not efficient enough; instead, before giving an employee an assignment, it is better to first ascertain that the person is best suited to perform the task, otherwise, it is advisable to find someone else whose skills and styles match the current needs.

Effective Communication

Every manager knows that communication is the key to a productive workforce. Technology has allowed us to contact each other with the mere click of a button (or tap of a touch screen). This seems to naturally mean that current communication methods are as efficient as possible, but, not necessarily. It is pertinent to note that a McKinsey study found that electronic mails can take up

nearly 28% of an employee's time. In fact, email was revealed to be the second most time-consuming activity for workers (after their job-specific tasks). Instead of relying solely on email, it is advisable to try social networking tools (such as Slack) designed for even quicker team communication. It is also okay to encourage the employees to occasionally adopt a more antiquated form of contact, e.g. voice-to-voice communication. Having a quick meeting or phone call can settle a matter that might have taken hours of back-and-forth electronic mails. Furthermore, a study conducted by Aruba in March, 2016 across 9 different countries and titled: "Mobility, Performance and Engagement" revealed that 42% of the employees believed that having easy and quick access to information was a good way to stay engaged at the workplace. The findings from the study also revealed how mobile technology had improved the communication process within the company, leading to better productivity. About 45% of the companies that provide technical support were among highly rated organizations, while just 17% of those that did not do so made the list. Effective communication also means that the employees are aware of the hierarchy of the organization and its vision. They should also know about the person or department they should reach out to for specific types of assistance.

Keeping Goals Clear & Focused

It is almost impossible to expect employees to be efficient if they do not have a focused goal to aim for. If a goal is not clearly defined and actually achievable, employees will be less productive; hence, ensuring that employees' assignments are as clear and narrow as possible is of utmost importance. They should be made to know exactly what is expected of them, and be told specifically what impact the assignment will have. One way to do this is to ensure that organizational set goals are "SMART" – specific, measurable, attainable, realistic, and time-bound. Therefore, before assigning an employee a task, it is good to know if such a task fits each

of these requirements; otherwise, the task can be tweaked to help the workers stay focused and efficient.

Incentivizing Employees

One of the best ways to encourage employees to be more efficient is to actually give them a reason to do so. If the company expects the staff to be motivated for the company's success, then, the company should be motivated for the staff's success. Recognizing the workers for a job well done will make them feel appreciated and encourage them to continue increasing their efficiency. Management should come up with different ways to motivate and reward the employees. An incentive structure should be designed to encourage the employees to work and achieve the targets. When deciding on how to reward efficient employees, their individual needs or preferences should be taken into consideration. The incentives need not be monetary all the time. For example, one employee might appreciate public recognition, while another would prefer a private "thank you." It can be in the form of a day off, liberty in working condition, gift vouchers or anything that can make the employee happy and willing to work for the company.

In addition to simple words of gratitude (and others mentioned above), below is a few set of incentives, which can be used to improve employees' efficiency:

- ***Paid Time Off (PTO):*** Instead of a bonus or raise, management can offer the employees an additional paid time off (PTO) without having to use their vacation or sick time.
- ***Take Them Out For a Meal:*** Employer can take the team out to lunch, dinner, or happy hour; or may even allow them to leave work early in order to do so.
- ***Send a Handwritten Note:*** Sending a handwritten note shows that management recognizes the great work the employees have done and that it cares enough to have put personal time into thanking them.

- ***Lazy Monday Coupons:*** Another option is a “Lazy Monday” coupon, which allows employees to arrive late on a Monday morning.
- ***Tell Your Boss:*** If the immediate supervisor emails the team or a team member, thanking them for their work, it is good to consider sending a copy of the electronic mail to the “boss”.
- ***Implement Workplace Wellness Programme:*** Consider implementing a workplace wellness program to cut down on the number of sick days and reduce the company’s overall health insurance spending.

Cutting out the Excess

If possible, employees should not be given smaller, unnecessary tasks when they are focused on a larger goal. A careful look at the team’s routine in order to see if there is anything that can be cut so as to give employees more time to focus on higher-priority assignments is necessary. For example, if employees are asked to write daily reports for their supervisors, but supervisors generally do not have time to read them, it is worth consideration cutting the report requirement. It is important to note that doing something simply as a formality is wasting valuable time that could be used for accomplishing goals that actually help the company.

Training and Developing Employees

Reducing training, or cutting it all together, might seem like a good way to save company time and money (learning on-the-job is said to be an effective way to train, after all). However, this could ultimately backfire. Forcing employees to learn their jobs on the fly can be extremely inefficient. So, instead of having workers haphazardly trying to accomplish a task with zero guidance, the organization should take the extra day to teach them the necessary skills to do their job. This way, they can set about accomplishing their tasks on their own, and they will not waste time down the road answering simple questions or correcting errors. Past their original training,

management should encourage continued employee development. Helping them expand their skill-sets will build a much more advanced workforce, which will benefit the company in the long run. There are a number of ways management can support employee development: individual coaching, workshops, courses, seminars, shadowing or mentoring, or even just increasing their responsibilities. Offering these opportunities will give employees additional skills that allow them to improve their efficiency and productivity.

Organized Breaks

People spend a majority of their time at the workplace, and hence, it is very important that they should be happy and relaxed during the working hours. According to the Bureau of Labour Statistics, Americans spend 8.8 hours a day in the workplace which is even more than the 7.7 hours spent on sleeping. Hence, a proper environment should be created so that the employees feel motivated to work. Proper and organized breaks should be given to the employees at regular intervals. Allowing the employees to spend some free time to relax and interact with each other can be a real help to increase the efficiency.

Embracing Telecommuting

Employees should be allowed to work from home when the need arises. Although, this might seem inefficient to the management because there is no guarantee that such employees will still be productive if no one is watching them, but, the reality is quite the opposite (in fact, studies show that people who work from home are 13% more productive than office employees). Allowing employees to telecommute will enable them to save time that would otherwise be wasted completely. For example, say an employee is feeling too ill to come in to work (or is simply worried about getting their co-workers sick) but can still be productive. If management disallows them to work from home, they will be forced to take a sick day and skip working all

together. In like manner, forcing employee to miss an entire day of work if they have to wait for that 2-4 hour period to get their refrigerator fixed is simply not efficient. Instead, management should allow such employee to work from home so they can maximize what time they do have available.

Giving Each Other Feedback

Employees may not perform well if the expectations are not communicated clearly to them. There is no hope of increasing employee efficiency if they do not know they are being inefficient in the first place. This is why performance reviews are essential – measuring the employees’ performance, then, holding individual meetings to let them know where they are excelling, and what areas they need work on. Increasing employee efficiency is not all about what they can do better – some of the responsibility falls on management as well. But, just like the employees, management is not psychic. So after reviewing the employees’ performance, management should ask them what it could do to help them improve. For instance, maybe they would like a little more guidance on certain tasks, or would prefer a little more room for creative freedom. Asking for feedback not only gives clear, immediate ways to help the employees improve, but also encourages a culture of open dialogue that will allow for continued development over time. Employees feel good when they realize that there is someone to understand their concerns and solve them. Quoting the former CEO of Xerox Corporation, “Employees who believe that management is concerned about them as a whole person – not just an employee – are more productive, more satisfied, more fulfilled. Satisfied employees mean satisfied customers, which leads to profitability.”

Think Big Picture

It is not always about now only, it is about after now also. Some things or activities might seem like an inefficient use of time now, but, they might actually be to the organization's advantage in the long run. So, before vetoing an apparent misuse of time, management should carefully find out how this could possibly benefit the organization. For instance, investing in human resources software now can save the company – and the employees – countless hours down the road. From automated onboarding to payroll that runs itself; embracing human resource information system (HRIS) technology, which will improve efficiency, reduce frustration, and help the business grow.

Reducing Meetings

The number of meetings should be minimized and avoided as they are said to be productivity killers. Many meetings are scheduled to share the updates, restrictions or policies which could have easily been communicated through the electronic mail. Meetings should be avoided if the purpose can be fulfilled through electronic mails or one-on-one discussions. For example: If 10 people attended the meeting that is scheduled to last for 1 hour, that translates to a loss of 10 hours to the firm. Hence, reducing the number of meetings can help save the crucial time of the employees. Firms should lay restriction on the maximum number of meetings to be scheduled during a given time period to ensure more efficiency.

Efficient Use of Technology

Efficient use of technology should be done to boost the efficiency of the employees and make the work easier. Tasks that are routine and mandatory should be automated as this can help save the time and manpower, which can be used to tackle the complex tasks associated with the business. Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) software is well known and widely used business process

management software that allows an organization to use a system of integrated applications to manage the business and automate many back office functions related to technology, services, and human resources. It not only reduces the cost of operations, but also makes the work easier for the employees.

Suitability of Office Design

A survey conducted by Gensler in 2016 on the US workplace environment revealed that 89% of the respondents considered office design an “important to very important”, while about 90% of the senior management considered an effective workplace design essential for employee productivity. It was also estimated that a company's productivity could be increased by 22% if the office was well-designed, however, as many as 40% of the employees believed that their companies had bad designs because they wanted to keep their costs as low as they could. About 46% of the respondents strongly believed that office design was not a part of their company's priority list and one out of five rated their work environment from “fair to poor”. About 90% of the employees admitted that the work environment affected the quality of their work and about 89% of them even went on to blame it for their job dissatisfaction. In actual fact, a spokesperson for Extra Office Interiors, in an interview once argued that even basic things like ergonomic workstations can make a huge difference to employee satisfaction and productivity.

Setting Goals & Communicating Its Achievement

Employees are more focused and motivated when they know exactly what is expected of them. It helps them in preparing a plan to achieve their targets. This is why it is important to clearly state the company's vision and mission and help the staff align themselves to these goals. Setting short-term goals can help management get the best out of its employees. It is equally important to provide them feedback so that they know their current situation and can make the necessary

adjustments. According to the US Office of Personnel Management, stating that an employee achieved 10% more than the target is more effective than saying “you are doing a good job”. At the same time, management should also point out employees’ failures to them and help them strategize to meet their targets better.

2.3.4 Seven Traits of an Efficient Employee

According to Nizamudheen (2017), a good employee is an asset to any organization because the key to the organization’s success is the effectiveness of the employees working in it. In such a scenario, it is vital to attach importance to employee satisfaction. It is always necessary to address the fair needs of an employee and attend to his/ her grievances to create job satisfaction, improve efficiency and a happy working environment. A happy employee is a productive employee and productivity is what contributes to the growth of any organization.

The following traits are distinctive of efficient employees (Nizamudheen, 2017):

Good Performance

The employee performance will speak for itself. Not only is there a good performance with little supervision but also willingness to take up additional responsibilities. Such employees do not require supervision and direction to complete tasks. They take up the ownership towards their work and derive satisfaction by completing tasks and being productive.

Professional Development

Efficient employees always look to develop themselves professionally by working towards improving their position. They actively participate in their career development programs and also keep up on the current industry trends. Their efficient work pays off and helps them climb the organizational ladder. They are concerned about the company’s performance and also offer ideas to improve the same.

Open Mindedness

Efficient employees have a positive attitude and an open mind. They are emotionally stable and have a consistent and efficient working and leadership style. They are quite composed even under pressure. An open mind enhances the learning capabilities of employees and also makes them good problem-solvers.

Optimism

They outperform the negative employees in productivity, energy levels and health care costs. Their approach is quite receptive and they are more successful and effective in handling clients than their negative counterparts.

Interpersonal Relations

A trait characteristic of efficient employees is their positive attitude towards their colleagues. They are quite cordial in maintaining healthy work relations with their team members. They are confident about their capabilities and also help other team members to improve themselves.

Feedback

Satisfied employees are receptive to feedback about their work as they constantly look forward to improving their skills and efficiency. They take healthy criticism in a positive way and look at it as an opportunity towards self-improvement.

Updated Knowledge

Satisfied employees keep their knowledge updated with the current trends and anything concerning the company - be it newsletters, advertisements, press coverage etc. This shows their interest and dedication towards the company even though their business position does not necessarily ask for it. The management should play an active role to have a positive effect on the

satisfaction of employees to enhance their efficiency. The employees no doubt would benefit but companies also stand the chance to gain from employee satisfaction due to their performance.

2.4 Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.2 depicts the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Figure 2.2 Conceptual framework
(Source: Self-made, 2018)

In the conceptual framework above, “performance incentives” is the independent variable having two aspects: financial incentives (proxied by base pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits, initiative rewards and special rewards, which were adopted from Huttu, 2010) and non-financial incentives (proxied by feedback to employees, recognition, employee participation, better work environment, career development and training, which were adapted from Bari, Arif & Shaib, 2013; Huttu, 2010; Oburu & Atambo, 2016; Sammer, 2011; Waqas & Saleem, 2014). It is hypothesised that if these elements are put into action, they may lead to an improvement in the aspect of employee efficiency as reflected in the dependent variable (proxied by accuracy, which was adopted from Fandom, 2017). The conceptual framework was designed to determine the effect of performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria.

2.5 Review of Empirical Studies

The review of empirical literatures on incentives as a source of motivation provides a consistent set of views on the effects of performance incentives on employee efficiency. Various studies predicted positive relationship between performance incentives and employee efficiency. Hence, this section is devoted to reviewing empirical studies on effect of performance incentives on employee efficiency conducted around the world in order to validate theoretical predictions.

Mukundi (2016) carried out a study to examine factors affecting employee productivity in private limited companies with a specific concentration at Equatorial Nut Processors Ltd (ENP). Institutional factors, environmental factors and employee characteristics were used as independent variables. Descriptive research design was adopted. The target population of the study were employees of the company and stratified sampling was adopted by dividing the target population into homogenous groups. In terms of data, the study relied on primary data collected using structured questionnaires that contained both open-ended and closed-ended questions. The study results show that institutional factors, environmental factors and personal characteristics affect employees' productivity. Regarding the institutional factors, the study established that organizational goal was the most contributing factor to higher employee productivity level. Work commitment level was the second followed by goal setting by the organization, meeting performance targets, innovation and problem solving capabilities. Other factors were teamwork and training of colleagues, organizational structure, and performance appraisal and employee motivation. In relation to environmental factors, it was established that satisfaction with the working environment was the major factor contributing to high level of productivity followed by supervisor support. The other factors were found to have slight effects on employee productivity. These are conflict between work and personal life, working infrastructure, promotion in the

organization, employee compatibility with organizational culture, organizational transparency, training & career development opportunities and pay and rewards. In relation to personal characteristics, it was established that employee training was the factor most contributing to high employee productivity, followed by employee relationship with colleagues, and age of employee. Other employee related factors found to affect employee productivity were marital status, gender and the education level of the employee. The study concluded that institutional factors help employee to perform at a high level, and, in relation to working environment, the study concluded that a satisfactory working environment and support from the supervisor will lead to high performance from the employee. Finally, the study inferred that a number of personal employees attributes (such as: training level of the employee, employee relationship with colleagues as well as the age of the employee) affect employee performance.

Al-Nsour (2012) investigated the relationship between incentives and organizational performance for employees in the Jordanian Universities. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software was used for descriptive analysis. Five universities (Amman Private University, Al-Balqa Applied University, Philadelphia University, Jerash University and Amman Arab University) from twenty-four universities were selected using 421 questionnaires. The main findings indicated that there is an adequate level of incentives provided to employees. Financial incentives ranked in 1st place while moral incentives ranked in the 2nd place. Also, it was found that there is a high level of organizational performance. Customer satisfaction ranked in the 1st place, internal business process in the 2nd place followed by learning and growth. There is relationship between financial & moral incentives and organizational performance as well as between financial & moral incentives and internal business process and customer satisfaction.

There is an effect of moral incentives on learning & growth but there is no relationship between financial incentives and learning & growth.

However, when Al-Harthi (1999) examined how financial and moral incentives can be used to raise efficiency of employees in the Department of Civil Defence in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, he found that financial and moral incentives are unsatisfactory and may lead to a decrease in the level of performance of employees. Promotion is the most important incentives affecting the efficiency of the employees, while financial incentives ranked first in importance to raise the efficiency of the performance of employees, followed by moral incentives.

Al-Aydi (2000) conducted a study to investigate the effect of incentives on the level of performance in the textile industry in Iraq. He found that there is a weak relationship between the incentives system and the level of performance and between the wages system and the level of performance; but, there is a strong correlation between rewards and the level of financial performance and between appropriate promotion system and level of performance.

Okwudili (2015) also examined the effect of non-monetary rewards on productivity of employees among selected government parastatals in Abia State, Southeast-Nigeria using simple random sampling technique of which data were gathered through questionnaire. Analytically, the study employed descriptive statistics, multiple regressions and the Pearson's correlation coefficient. The analysis of factors affecting productivity of employees in Government parastatals in the study area using the multiple regression analysis indicated that sex of the respondents, age of respondents, monthly income, days of work in a month, type of non-monetary reward received and responses of respondents with respect to their judgment on effect of non-monetary reward on their productivity all revealed a negative significant contribution to their productivity. However, marital status of the respondents, educational qualification of the

respondents, position/rank, and number of non-monetary reward received revealed a positive significant contribution all at one percent (1%) level of probability respectively to the productivity of the employees. The Pearson's correlation coefficient values indicated that non-monetary rewards and productivity of employees have a positive relationship which is significant at 5% level of probability (2-tailed). The study concludes that higher productivity and efficiency of employees in government parastatals is possible with the effective exploitation of human resources through non-monetary rewards and recommends amongst others that Government should motivate their staff more by involving them in self developmental programs with good remuneration payment, incentive packages, among others, that will signify that the organization needs their personal outputs.

Huttu (2010) studied how different incentives affect performance and job satisfaction. In the study, the effects of recognition, participation, feedback, monetary incentives, non-monetary tangible incentives and benefits on performance and job satisfaction were researched. It was posited that different incentives have different effects on performance and job satisfaction. Incentives effect on performance and job satisfaction were researched through critical literature review and interview research. The study found that there are two different aspects in rewarding. These two aspects are effectiveness and humanity. Effectiveness-aspect means that employees feel that they are justified to get monetary incentives because they have put extra effort on work while the humanity-aspect means that it is important that employees feel that employer is interested in employees, their work and well-being. The rewarding of the humanity-aspect is more important in generating job satisfaction whereas the rewarding of the effectiveness-aspect affects performance. Different incentives affect different aspects in a different way. Hence, different incentives have different effects on performance and job satisfaction like it was posited.

Finally, the study found that these aspects (i.e. the effectiveness-aspect and the humanity-aspect) complement each other, and as a result, suggesting a comprehensive rewarding.

Waqar, Sana, Kashif and Ahson (2018) conducted a study on measuring the non-financial rewards in escalating employees' job satisfaction: a study of private companies in Pakistan in 2018. The study measures the impact of non-financial rewards on job satisfaction at workplace in private companies of Karachi City, Pakistan. Data was gathered through self-administrated questionnaire containing 5 nominal and 12 Likert scale questions from a sample of 100 employees using the convenience sampling technique. The data was analysed through the SPSS. Correlation and regression tests were applied to analyze the data. The results revealed that recognition, flexible working arrangement, feedback to employees, freedom, advancement opportunities, promotion, empowerment, competitive work environment and individual reward preference positively impacted job satisfaction in the workplace.

Awan and Tahir (2015) studied the impact of working environment on employee's productivity: a case study of Banks and Insurance Companies in Pakistan and found that the level of productivity can be increased through developing a conducive working environment in the organization. The basic objective of the study was to measure the impact of working environment on productivity of employees. The organizations like banks and insurance companies were selected for conducting the study. A closed-ended questionnaire was developed to get feedback from target audience and different statistical methods were used to derive results from the collected data. It was observed that the factors like supervisor support, relation with co-workers, training and development, attractive and fast incentives and recognition plans, adequate workload at work place are helpful in developing a working environment that has positive impact on employee's level of productivity in the organizations.

2.5.1 Relationship between Financial Performance Incentives and Employee Efficiency

According to the study of Al-Nsour (2012), there is a significant positive relationship between financial & moral incentives and organizational performance. However, Al-Harthi (1999) found in his study that financial and moral incentives are unsatisfactory and may lead to a decrease in the level of performance of employees.

2.5.2 Relationship between Non-financial Performance Incentives and Employee Efficiency

Okwudili (2015) found that non-monetary rewards and productivity of employees have a positive relationship. Furthermore, Woodruffe (2006) found that non-monetary incentives can motivate employees to give a greater job performance. Bari, Arif and Shaib (2013) have also found a significant positive relationship between non-financial rewards and employee attitude and performance. Rajendran, Mosisa and Nedelea (2017) have also concluded in their recent study that there are relationships between non-monetary benefits and employees work performance. Also, Oburu and Atambo (2016) found in their study that non-financial compensation promotes employee performance.

2.6 Theoretical Review

Understanding motivation theories is important in understanding the effects of performance incentives on employee efficiency because motivation theories are the base of rewarding. There are various theories of motivation on which this study can be rooted. However, only the most relevant ones to this study are considered. Hence, this study is rooted in such motivational theories as: Victor H. Vroom's Expectancy Theory and the Stacy J. Adam's Equity Theory.

2.6.1 The Expectancy Theory

The expectancy theory is an improvement on the previous theories of McGregor, Herzberg and Abraham Maslow. According to Vroom (1964), expectancy theory has suggested that the effect

of task incentives on motivation is dependent on personal values. Vroom's theory explains that the goals of employees do enhance and influence their inputs, and that the behaviour will genuinely lead to the goals (Nigeria Institute of Management, n.d.). Vroom (1964) asserted that the strength of a tendency to act in a certain way depends on the strength of an expectation that the act will be followed by a given outcome and on the attractiveness of the outcome to the individual (Vroom, 1964). Another important motivational fact is that, in general, people will not pursue rewards they find unattractive, or engage in tasks on which the odds of success are very low. Psychologist Victor Vroom's motivation theory echoes these commonsense observations. He says a person's motivation to exert some level of effort is a function of three things: the person's expectancy (in terms of probability) that his/her effort will lead to performance; instrumentality, or the perceived connection (if any) between successful performance and actually obtaining the rewards; and valence, which represents the perceived value the person attaches to the reward (Dessler, 2005). In other words, a person's expectation that his/her effort will lead to performance is expectancy. The perceived relationships between successful performance and obtaining the reward refer to instrumentality while the perceived value a person attaches to the reward is valence (Dessler, 2005). Kurfi (2013) argued that valence entails the importance or desirability of an outcome or reward that an individual places that can be achieved on the job tasks performance while instrumentality entails the individual perception that his action, effort or behaviour at particular level will lead to attainment of a particular outcome and expectancy entails the perceived probability by an individual that his effort will result in a certain level of performance. Personnel will be motivated to perform at a high level if their expectancy is high. Vroom averred that the effort to satisfy one's needs would depend on the person's perception that he can expect the effort to be followed by a certain outcome, which will bring

desirable rewards (Nigeria Institute of Management, n.d.). In Vroom's theory, motivation is thus, a product of three things i.e. $Motivation = (E \times I \times V)$, where, of course, E represents expectancy, I, Instrumentality, and V, Valence. If E or I or V is zero or inconsequential, there will be no motivation (Dessler, 2005). According to the Nigeria Institute of Management (n.d.), Taylor (1974) adduces the following issues inherent in Vroom's theory:

- a. What kind of behaviour must the employee produce in order to achieve these objectives?
- b. What outcome does the job offer the employee?
- c. How attractive do employees view these outcomes?

Implications of Vroom's Expectancy Theory

- i. It implies that management should counsel subordinates to help them grasp a realistic view of their competency.
- ii. Management must support and encourage the subordinates in developing those skills that are important in leading them to better performance.
- iii. Rewards and pay should always be remembered.
- iv. The individual should not forget what is expected of him.
- v. It lays emphasis on the attractiveness of rewards.

Dessler (2005) asserts that Vroom's theory has three implications for how managers design pay-for-performance plans. First (looking first at just "E"), if employees do not expect that effort will produce performance, no motivation will occur. So, managers must ensure that their employees have the skills to do the job, and believe they can do the job. That is why training, job descriptions, and confidence building and support are important. Second (with respect to "I"), Vroom's theory also suggests that employees must see the instrumentality of their efforts – they must believe that successful performance will, in fact, lead to getting the reward. Managers can

accomplish these in many ways – by creating easy-to-understand incentive plans, and by communicating success stories so that employees see they will be rewarded for doing well. Last but not least (with respect to "V"); the reward itself must be of value to employee. Here (as explained above), the manager should take individual employee preferences into account, and endeavour to use extrinsic and intrinsic reward that make sense, in terms of the specific behaviour that is to be encouraged (Dessler, 2005).

The expectancy theory has four inherent steps for its application in the workplace (Kurfi, 2013):

- i. Determination of the outcome that the job offers to the personnel whether positive or negative. Positive outcomes include pay, security, promotional opportunities, exploiting of one's talents or skills, congenial associations and benefits. The negative outcomes include frustration, fatigue, boredom, harsh supervisions, threat of dismissal and anxiety. All these are based on the personal perceptions of the personnel, which may be accurate or otherwise.
- ii. Determination of the extent to which the personnel view these outcomes as attractive to them. The attractiveness could be positive, negative or neutral. Of course, attractiveness is an internal issue to the personnel, which depends on their needs, personal values and personality. If the attractiveness is valued positive, personnel would work towards attaining it; if it is valued negative, the reverse would be the case, or the personnel could be neutral as the case may be.
- iii. Determination of the kind of behaviour to be displayed by the personnel to achieve the desired outcomes. The management would assess the factors determining the effort an individual puts into his job, the relationship between efforts and performance, the value of the rewards attached to performance and the probability that rewards depend on effort.

- iv. Determination of how do personnel view their chances of doing what is asked of them to accomplish or to obtain what will fulfil their needs or desires. These depend on the personnel skills, compensation and dispositions, and their ability to control those variables that will determine their success.

According to DeCenzo and Robins (as cited in Kurfi, 2013), simplified expectancy approach can be described as follows: an individual effort would be exerted when it is perceived that it would lead to effective performance that would lead to organizational reward, which is attractive to satisfy the individual's goals or needs.

Figure 2.3 Simplified Expectancy Model
(Source: DeCenzo, D.A. & Robins S.P., 2003, p. 321)

The expectancy theory is a contingency approach, which recognizes that there is no universal method for motivating personnel (Kurfi, 2013). However, according to Cole (as cited in Kurfi, 2013), managers who wish to make use of the ideas embodied in the expectancy theory will need to consider the following:

- i. How can personnel preferences and values be identified?
- ii. What rewards are most likely to be valued by personnel?
- iii. In what ways can rewards be tied to performance?
- iv. How can available rewards be published?
- v. What training resources are required to ensure that personnel efforts can result in effective performance?
- vi. How can jobs be redesigned so as to incorporate the rewards sought by personnel?

2.6.2 The Equity Theory

Adams (1963) cited in Kurfi (2013) argued that if personnel perceived that they are being treated equitably, their work efforts are sustained; but, if they perceived that they are not being treated equitably in relation to their inputs and the inputs of other comparable personnel, their work efforts declined. The Equity Theory tries to explain what happens when personnel thought of an imbalance between what they put into a job and what they get out of it vis-à-vis others' give and get ratio. Thus, equity exists when an employee perceive that the ratio of outcomes to inputs is in equilibrium both internally with respect to self and in relation to others. Flippo (as cited in Kurfi, 2013) proposes nine different situations to explain equity theory as in figure 2.4.

Gross Over-reward (1)	Moderate Over-reward (2)	Equity (3)
Moderate Over-reward (4)	Equity (5)	Moderate Under-reward (6)
Equity (7)	Moderate Under-reward (8)	Gross Under-reward (9)
Low	Medium	High

Figure 2.4 Equity in Compensation
(Source: Flippo, E.B., 1984, p. 286)

According to Kurfi (2013), one can see from the figure above that equity theory would hypothesize that the correlation of compensation (i.e. pay) and contribution (i.e. input) that exists in cells 3, 5 and 7 would result in feelings of equity, whereas, in all other cells, feelings of

dissonance are likely to exist. Thus, with respect to under-reward situations (such as cells 6, 8 and 9), it clearly shows that personnel satisfaction would be lower than in either the equity or over-reward situations because personnel contributions (i.e. efforts and inputs) exceed their outcomes (particularly monetary compensations). This would result into dissatisfaction, which often leads to efforts to establish equilibrium. However, concerning the over-reward situations, Adams suggested that feelings of discomfort and guilt resulting from inequitably higher pay would lead to action to reduce dissonance. Sometimes, there are indications of guilt from those receiving more rewards than they deserve, but, such feelings are not translated into actions in terms of more productivity. As such, many organizations pursue a pay increase policy characterized by cells 4, 5 and 6. The personnel of average contributions are accorded an average increase in pay while those above and below average are allocated compensation amount not significantly different. Thus, inferior personnel are moderately over-rewarded, leading to little or no change in productivity but effecting acceptable level of satisfaction. However, superior personnel are moderately under-rewarded leading to lower contributions or withdrawal from the organization. According to Adams' Equity Theory, an individual can alter their quality and quantity of work to restore justice when they perceive the outcome-input ratio not to be just (Adams, 1966).

Dixon and Lim (2012) cited in Mukundi (2016) emphasized that the equity theory suggested that managers should promote high levels of motivation by ensuring that employees believe in the outcomes. For instance, salaries should be distributed in proportion to inputs that include time and effort. Sire and Balkon (2000) and Salimäki, Hakonen and Heneman (2009) in their studies (as cited in Huttu, 2010) argued that equity can be divided into distributive justice and procedural justice. Distributive justice refers to equity with co-workers. This means that employees'

incentives should be relative to reference group. Procedural justice in turn refers to the means according to which incentives are distributed to employees. It can also be talked about as external and internal comparison (Salimäki et al. 2009, as cited in Huttu, 2010). Based on external comparison, satisfaction depends on the comparison of individual's outcome-input ratio to the ratio of co-workers (Adams 1965, as cited in Huttu, 2010). Internal comparison, however, refers to individual's perception of what he should get and what he actually got. Internal comparison shares similar thoughts with the expectancy theory. If employee feels that incentives are unfair, they would be less satisfied with them (Huttu, 2010).

DeCenzo and Robbins (2003) cited in Kurfi (2013) argued that when personnel perceived inequity, they may choose one or more of five alternatives:

- i. Distort either their own or others' input or outcomes.
- ii. Behave in some way so as to induce others to change inputs or outcomes.
- iii. Behave in some way as to change their inputs or outcomes.
- iv. Choose a different comparison referent.
- v. Leave the organization.

Kurfi (2013) asserted that the implication of the equity theory is that organizations need provide a system of equitable compensation for their personnel. Furthermore, if management wants motivated personnel, regardless of any negotiations with trade unions, then, they must ensure that compensation for efforts, other things being equal, are seen as fair by all personnel.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the procedures employed for the collection and analysis of the data relevant to the investigation. These include: research design, population of the study, sample size and sampling technique, source of data, methods of data collection and method of data analysis.

3.2 Research Design

This research adopted the cross-sectional survey research design, which is descriptive in nature. Descriptive research is best used where the problem is well-defined, there exists information about the phenomenon, and the researcher can be involved in a survey by going to the target population in order for the respondents to explain certain features about the problem under study (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). According to Orodho (2009), descriptive research is advantageous because it is time-saving and efficient in obtaining current factual information from respondents. Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) further argued that descriptive research describes and reports things such as possible behaviour, attitudes, values and characteristics the way they are. For instance, this research is centred on the efficiency of employees with a view to establishing how it is affected by performance incentives whether positively or negatively. This helps to create an understanding on how the study area (Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria) can increase their employees' efficiency level. The rationale for using descriptive research design was that the research questions require an examination of employee efficiency and how it is affected by performance incentives. This requires examination of the various constructs and their relationship with the dependent variable. Hence, descriptive research design was appropriate for this study.

3.3 Population of the Study

The target population of this study comprised all the staff of the Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State in Northwest-Nigeria. All categories of staff (upper, middle and lower cadres) were included in the study. Determination of the target population considers the following elements: the ease of access and data collection; and the extent to which the subject of research affects the said target (Shaw, 2012). It requires an epistemological consideration which describes how the target population relates to the knowledge being sought. For example, while an expert would be knowledgeable by virtue of having studied the subject over time, the employees would contain experiential knowledge since they are the ones whose efficiency is being examined (Mukundi, 2016). The population size of the study is, therefore, sixty employees. The breakdown of the study population distribution is provided in table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Study Population Distribution

S/N	DMBs IN DUTSIN-MA LGA	UPPER CADRE	MIDDLE CADRE	LOWER CADRE	TOTAL
1.	First Bank Limited	5	7	9	21
2.	United Bank for Africa	4	6	10	20
3.	Unity Bank PLC	4	7	8	19
	Total	13	20	27	60

Source: Field Survey (2018)

3.4 Sample Size & Sampling Technique

3.4.1 Sample Size

In this study, the researcher obtained a sample size of 52 employees (using the Taro Yamane, 1967 statistical formula) from all the Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State,

Northwest-Nigeria, to represent the entire population of the study. A sample size between 50 and 400 observations is adequate to represent a given study population (Hair, Anderson, Tatham, & Black, 1998). Hence, the sample size for the study is adequate since it falls between the range of 50 and 400 observations.

The determination of an adequate sample size from the finite population of the study, using the Yamane (1967) statistical formula, is given below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size

1 = constant value

e = margin of error (= 0.05)

$$\therefore n = \frac{60}{1 + 60(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{60}{1 + 60(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{60}{1 + .15}$$

$$n = \frac{60}{1.15}$$

$$n = 52.1739 \underline{\underline{= 52}}$$

Therefore, from the above calculation, the sample size of the study is fifty-two (52) employees.

3.4.2 Sampling Technique

Proportional stratum allocation technique and the simple random sampling technique were used in this study. The use of proportional stratum allocation technique was because the technique produces a representative sample as the study population was heterogeneous while the use of

simple random technique was because the population contained a finite number of elements, was mutually exclusive and the population in each stratum was homogeneous.

The final sample for this study is shown in table 3.2.

Table 3.2 Sample Size Distribution

S/N	Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA	Upper Cadre		Middle Cadre		Lower Cadre		Total	
		*P	Sample	*P	Sample	*P	Sample	*P	Sample
1.	First Bank Limited	5	4	7	6	9	8	21	18
2.	United Bank for Africa PLC	4	4	6	5	10	8	20	17
3.	Unity Bank PLC	4	4	7	6	8	7	19	17
4.	Total	13	12	20	17	27	23	60	52

*Population

3.5 Sources & Method of Data Collection

The study collected primary data through structured questionnaire that contained closed-ended questions. The study used a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire to collect study data. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. The first section was devoted to demographic characteristics of the respondents such as gender, age, academic and professional qualifications, employment status, length of service in the bank, among others. The second section was subdivided into three parts. Part one sought to examine whether the Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State encourage employees through performance incentives; part two sought to determine effect of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State while part three sought to evaluate effect of nonfinancial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State.

The first section of the questionnaire had 8 items while the second section consisted of 24 paragraphs, which were devoted to measuring the independent and dependent variables. Paragraphs 1-12 measured the performance incentives Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State adopt to encourage employees; paragraphs 13-18 measured effect of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State; and paragraphs 19-24 measured effect of nonfinancial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State.

3.6 Validity and Reliability of Data Collection Instrument

3.6.1 Validity

The validity of a scale refers to the degree to which it measures what it is supposed to measure. Unfortunately, there is no one clear-cut indicator of a scale's validity. The validation of a scale involves the collection of empirical evidence concerning its use or verification of the scale by a number of professionals in the area of research (Brimah, 2018). Hence, to validate the scales of the instrument used, the researcher e-mailed the questionnaire to Management Professors from the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (UDUS) and the Bayero University, Kano (BUK) for review and to verify the validity of the paragraphs. After the questionnaire was reviewed and returned by e-mail, necessary corrections were made to paragraphs nine and eleven (part one) and paragraph one (part three) in section b; and the researcher had also rewritten paragraph ten (part one) as well as paragraph five (part two) and paragraph five (part three) of the same section.

3.6.2 Reliability

The reliability of a scale refers to the degree to which the items that make up the scale 'hang together' and measure the same underlying construct. One of the most commonly used indicators of reliability is Cronbach's alpha coefficient (Brimah, 2018). Ideally, the Cronbach alpha

coefficient of a scale should be close to 0.7 (Pallant, 2005 as cited by Brimah, 2018). Cronbach's α (alpha) as a coefficient of reliability was used to measure the internal consistency for all variables in this study. Hence, α for performance incentives Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State adopt to encourage employees was 0.86; effect of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State, 0.52 and effect of nonfinancial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State, 0.51. Coefficients ranged between 0.51 and 0.86. According to Brimah (2018), with short scales (e.g. scales with fewer than ten items), it is common to find quite low Cronbach alpha values (e.g. 0.5). In this case, it may be more appropriate to report the mean inter-item correlation for the items. Briggs and Cheek (1986 as cited by Brimah, 2018) recommend an optimal range for the inter-item correlation of 0.2 to 0.4. Hence, the inter-item correlation of the scales for effect of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency and effect of nonfinancial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State was done.

3.7 Method of Data Analysis

Data collected was in the form of quantitative data. After collection, the data was coded and cleaned before being analyzed. Since the analysed data were categorical in nature and in Likert format, a combination of chi-square and percentages were used for the analysis. Percentages were used for the descriptive analysis while chi-square was used to establish relationships among variables and see the significance of the relationship between them. Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 20 (SPSS v.20) was used to analyze the data.

3.8 Measurement of Variables

There are two variables used in this study: performance incentives, which is the independent variable having two aspects: financial incentives (proxied by base pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits, initiative rewards and special rewards, which were adopted from Huttu, 2010) and nonfinancial incentives (proxied by feedback to employees, recognition, employee participation, better work environment, career development and training, which were adapted from Bari, Arif & Shaib, 2013; Huttu, 2010; Oburu & Atambo, 2016; Sammer, 2011; Waqas & Saleem, 2014); employee efficiency, which is the dependent variable (proxied by speed, which was adopted from Fandom, 2017).

3.9 Summary of Chapter

This chapter has provided the study design and methodology adopted in this study. These included the research design, population of the study, sample size and sampling technique, sources of data collection, instrument of data collection, validity and reliability of instrument of data collection, method of data analysis and measurement of variables.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the analysis of the primary data obtained through questionnaires administered on the employees of the three Deposit Money Banks (vis-à-vis First Bank, United Bank for Africa and Unity Bank) in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria is presented. A total of fifty-two (52) questionnaires were distributed to the respondents for this study and all the fifty-two (52) questionnaires were duly completed and returned. Each of the hypotheses earlier formulated was tested and the eventual findings were discussed. Furthermore, the result of the analysis laid the foundation for the interpretation and recommendation.

4.2 Data Presentation

4.2.1 Respondents' Demographic Characteristics

Frequency distribution of the respondents' demographic characteristics is presented in table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Frequency Distribution of the Respondents' Demographic Characteristics

Characteristics	Category	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative percent
Gender	Female	8	15.4	15.4
	Male	44	84.6	100.0
	Total	52	100.0	
Age Group (in years)	20 – 25	4	7.7	7.7
	26 – 30	19	36.5	44.2
	31 – 35	16	30.8	75.0
	36 – 40	10	19.2	94.2
	41 and above	3	5.8	100.0

	Total	52	100.0	
Highest Academic Qualification	Ordinary Level	4	7.7	7.7
	OND/NCE	7	13.5	21.2
	HND/Bachelor's Degree	32	61.5	82.7
	MBA	1	1.9	84.6
	Master's Degree	8	15.4	100.0
	Total	52	100.0	
Professional Qualification	Yes	8	15.4	15.4
	No	44	84.6	100.0
	Total	52	100.0	
Employment Status	Permanent Staff	28	53.8	53.8
	Casual Staff	6	11.5	65.4
	Contract Staff	18	34.6	100.0
	Total	52	100.0	
Total Years of Work Experience as a Bank Staff	Below 1 Year	6	11.5	11.5
	1 – 5	16	30.8	42.3
	6 – 10	28	53.8	96.2
	11 – 20	2	3.8	100.0
	Total	52	100.0	
Length of Service in this Bank	Below 1 Year	7	13.5	13.5
	1 – 2	8	15.4	28.8
	3 – 5	10	19.2	48.1
	6 – 10	23	44.2	92.3

	11 – 15	3	5.8	98.1
	Above 15 Years	1	1.9	100.0
	Total	52	100.0	
Monthly Net Pay (₦)	Below 20,000	1	1.9	1.9
	20,001 – 40,000	14	26.9	28.8
	40,001 – 60,000	5	9.6	38.5
	60,001 – 80,000	3	5.8	44.2
	80,001 – 100,000	11	21.2	65.4
	Above 100,000	18	34.6	100.0
	Total	52	100.0	

Source: Author's Fieldwork Computation Using SPSS 20.0, 2018

Table 4.1 shows that out of the 52 respondents, 8 (15.4%) were female while 44 (84.6%) were male. By implication, there were more male respondents than female respondents in the sample. Furthermore, out of the 52 respondents, 4 (7.7%) were aged between 20 – 25 years, 19 (36.5%) were aged between 26 – 30 years, 16 (30.8%) were aged between 31 – 35 years, 10 (19.2%) were aged between 36 – 40 years, 3 (5.8%) were aged from 41 years and above. Also, 4 (7.7%) were Ordinary Level Certificate holders, 7 (13.5%) OND/NCE holders, 32 (61.5%) HND/Bachelor's Degree holders, 1 (1.9%) MBA holder and 8 (15.4%) were Master's Degree holders out of the 52 respondents. By implication, majority of the respondents had high educational qualification. However, only 8 (15.4%) out of the 52 respondents had professional qualifications while the remaining 44 (84.6%) had no professional qualification. By implication, majority of the respondents had no professional qualification. There were 28 (53.8%) permanent staff, 6 (11.5%) casual staff and 18 (34.6%) contract staff out of the 52 respondents. By implication, there were

more permanent staff than the casual and contract staffs combined. On the aspect of work experience as bank staff, out of the 52 respondents, 6 (11.5%) had below 1 year, 16 (30.8%) had between 1 and 5 years, 28 (53.8%) had between 6 and 10 years while 2 (3.8%) had between 11 and 20 years of work experience as bank staff. By implication, there were more experienced employees as respondents in the sample. In like manner, the 52 respondents' lengths of service with the bank were as follows: 7 (13.5%), below 1 year; 8 (15.4%), between 1 and 2 years; 10 (19.2%), between 3 and 5 years; 23 (44.2%), between 6 and 10 years; 3 (5.8%), between 11 and 15 years and 1 (1.9%), above 15 years. By implication, majority of the respondents had worked with the bank for at least, 6 years. On the aspect of monthly net pay, 1 (1.9%) earned below ₦20,000, 14 (26.9%), between ₦20,001 and ₦40,000; 5 (9.6%), between ₦40,001 and ₦60,000; 3 (5.8%), between ₦60,001 and ₦80,000; 11 (21.2%), between ₦80,001 and ₦100,000 while 18 (34.6%) earned above ₦100,000. By implication, majority of the respondents earned at least, ₦80,000.

4.2.2 Performance Incentives Adopted by Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State to Encourage Employees

The study sought to examine whether the Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area encourage employees through performance incentives. To this effect, the respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

The result is shown in table 4.2.

Table 4.2 Performance Incentives Adopted by Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State to Encourage Employees

Performance incentives adopted by Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State to encourage employees	SD	D	U	A	SA
This bank provides its employees with a basic payment that is commensurate to their respective grade levels.	1 (1.9%)	5 (9.6%)	9 (17.3%)	21 (40.4%)	16 (30.8%)
This bank pays its employees a proportion of its profit before interest and tax (PBIT) as a form of profit sharing.	5 (9.6%)	6 (11.5%)	17 (32.7%)	16 (30.8%)	8 (15.4%)
When an employee meets up with or exceeds targets, this bank gives them some amount of money other than the basic pay as a form of gain sharing.	7 (13.5%)	9 (17.3%)	9 (17.3%)	18 (34.6%)	9 (17.3%)
This bank provides benefits such as official car, official house, life assurance, private medical care and annual holiday entitlement to its employees.	Nil	7 (13.5%)	9 (17.3%)	16 (30.8%)	20 (38.5%)

This bank rewards its employees for using their own initiatives when they are faced with challenges as regards the task assigned to them.	4 (7.7%)	8 (15.4%)	17 (32.7%)	18 (34.6%)	5 (9.6%)
This bank gives its employees special rewards in form of an all-expense-paid trip to a specific place of interest and tickets to sports events/cinemas.	3 (5.8%)	11 (21.2%)	17 (32.7%)	14 (26.9%)	7 (13.5%)
This bank gives its employees feedback on how efficient they are with regard to the tasks assigned to them.	1 (1.9%)	3 (5.8%)	16 (30.8%)	16 (30.8%)	16 (30.8%)
This bank gives due recognition such as employee of the month/year, "thank you", certificate of recognition and gift items to employees who efficiently do their work.	4 (7.7%)	10 (19.2%)	8 (15.4%)	14 (26.9%)	16 (30.8%)
In this bank, employees participate in decisions regarding their job design and other decisions as they affect employees' work.	4 (7.7%)	5 (9.6%)	14 (26.9%)	19 (36.5%)	10 (19.2%)
The working environment in this bank, such as supervisor's/branch	Nil	5 (9.6%)	8 (15.4%)	22 (42.3%)	17 (32.7%)

manager's support is okay.					
This bank gives employees enough opportunity to develop their careers.	5 (9.6%)	7 (13.5%)	10 (19.2%)	19 (36.5%)	11 (21.2%)
This bank gives employees relevant trainings so that the employees can acquire necessary knowledge & skills required in carrying out the task assigned to them.	2 (3.8%)	2 (3.8%)	9 (17.3%)	19 (36.5%)	20 (38.5%)

Source: Author's Fieldwork Computation Using SPSS 20.0, 2018

The findings shown in table 4.2 indicates that 1 (1.9%) of the respondents strongly disagree that the deposit money banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA provide their employees with a basic payment that is commensurate to their respective grade levels, while 5 (9.6%) disagreed, 9 (17.3%) undecided, 21 (40.4%) agreed and 16 (30.8%) strongly agreed. It also shows 5 (9.6%) strongly disagree, 6 (11.5%) disagree, 17 (32.7%) undecided, 16 (30.8%) agree and 8 (15.4%) strongly agree that the deposit money banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA pay their employees a proportion of their profit before interest and tax (PBIT) as a form of profit sharing. Furthermore, it shows 7 (13.5%) strongly disagree, 9 (17.3%) disagree, 9 (17.3%) undecided, 18 (34.6%) agree and 9 (17.3%) strongly agree that the deposit money banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA give employees some amount of money other than the basic pay as a form of gain sharing when employees meet up with or exceed targets. On whether the deposit money banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA provide benefits such as official car, official house, life assurance, private medical care and annual holiday entitlements to their employees, the table shows that 7 (13.5%) disagree, 9 (17.3%) undecided, 16 (30.8%) agree while 20 (38.5%) strongly agree. The table further shows that 4 (7.7%) strongly disagree, 8

(15.4%) disagree, 17 (32.7%) undecided, 18 (34.6%) agree while 5 (9.6%) strongly agree that the deposit money banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA reward their employees for using their own initiatives when they are faced with challenges as regards the task assigned to them. The respondents were further asked if the deposit money banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA give their employees special rewards in form of an all-expense-paid trip to a specific place of interest and tickets to sports events/cinemas and the table shows that 3 (5.8%) strongly disagree, 11 (21.2%) disagree, 17 (32.7%) undecided, 14 (26.9%) agree while 7 (13.5%) strongly agree. Furthermore, of the 52 respondents, 1 (1.9%) strongly disagree, 3 (5.8%) disagree, 16 (30.8%) undecided, 16 (30.8%) agree, 16 (30.8%) strongly agree that the deposit money banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA give their employees feedback on how efficient they are with regard to the tasks assigned to them. When the respondents were asked whether the deposit money banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA give due recognition such as: employee of the month/year, "thank you", certificate of recognition and gift items to employees who efficiently do their work, 4 (7.7%) strongly disagree, 10 (19.2%) disagree, 8 (15.4%) undecided, 14 (26.9%) agree while 16 (30.8%) strongly agree. From the 52 respondents, the table also shows that 4 (7.7%) strongly disagree, 5 (9.6%) disagree, 14 (26.9%) undecided, 19 (36.5%) agree and 10 (19.2%) strongly agree that the deposit money banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA allow employees to participate in decisions regarding their job design and other decisions that affect their work. Also, 5 (9.6%) disagree, 8 (15.4%) undecided, 22 (42.3%) agree and 17 (32.7%) strongly agree that the working environment in Deposit money banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA such as supervisor's/branch manager's support is okay. Furthermore, 5 (9.6%) strongly disagree, 7 (13.5%) disagree, 10 (19.2%) undecided, 19 (36.5%) agree and 11 (21.2%) strongly agree that the deposit money banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA give their employees enough opportunity to develop their careers. Finally, 2 (3.8%) strongly disagree, 2 (3.8%) disagree, 9 (17.3%)

undecided, 19 (36.5%) agree and 20 (38.5%) strongly agree that the deposit money banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA give their employees relevant trainings so that the employees can acquire necessary knowledge & skills required in carrying out the task assigned to them.

4.2.3 Effects of Financial Performance Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State

The study sought to examine effect of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State. To this effect, the respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The result is shown in table 4.3.

Table 4.3 Effects of Financial Performance Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State

Effect of Financial Performance Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State	SD	D	U	A	SA
The financial incentives my bank gives its employees, such as base pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits, initiative rewards and special rewards are adequate.	2 (3.8%)	11 (21.2%)	16 (30.8%)	18 (34.6%)	5 (9.6%)
Before my bank gives the financial incentives, employee efficiency	4 (7.7%)	12 (23.1%)	20 (38.5%)	12 (23.1%)	4 (7.7%)

remains the same.					
As soon as my bank gives its employees financial incentives, employee efficiency improves.	Nil	4 (7.7%)	11 (21.2%)	20 (38.5%)	17 (32.7%)
Without the financial incentives, employees in this bank are not willing to increase the speed at which they work.	6 (11.5%)	7 (13.5%)	22 (42.3%)	12 (23.1%)	5 (9.6%)
Employees in this bank do their works with no errors because of the financial incentives given to them.	2 (3.8%)	6 (11.5%)	19 (36.5%)	16 (30.8%)	9 (17.3%)
This bank should continue giving its employees financial performance incentives in order to make the employees increase their efficiency.	3 (5.8%)	Nil	9 (17.3%)	25 (48.1%)	15 (28.8%)

Source: Author's Fieldwork Computation Using SPSS 20.0, 2018

The findings shown in table 4.3 indicates 2 (3.8%) strongly disagree, 11 (21.2%) disagree, 16 (30.8%) undecided, 18 (34.6%) agree and 5 (9.6%) strongly agree that the financial incentives the Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA give their employees, such as base pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits, initiative rewards and special rewards are adequate. Also, 4 (7.7%) strongly disagree, 12 (23.1%) disagree, 20 (38.5%) undecided, 12 (23.1%) agree and 4 (7.7%) strongly agree that employee efficiency remain the same before the Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA give their employees financial incentives. When the 52 respondents

were asked whether as soon as the Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA give their employees financial incentives employee efficiency improves, 4 (7.7%) disagree, 11 (21.2%) undecided, 20 (38.5%) agree while 17 (32.7%) strongly agree. The table further shows 6 (11.5%) strongly disagree, 7 (13.5%) disagree, 22 (42.3%) undecided, 12 (23.1%) agree and 5 (9.6%) strongly agree that without the financial incentives, employees in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA are not willing to increase the speed at which they work. Out of the 52 respondents, 2 (3.8%) strongly disagree, 6 (11.5%) disagree, 19 (36.5%) undecided, 16 (30.8%) agree and 9 (17.3%) strongly agree that employees in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA do their works with no errors because of the financial incentives given to them. Finally, 3 (5.8%) strongly disagree, 9 (17.3%) undecided, 25 (48.1%) agree while 15 (28.8%) strongly agree that the Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA should continue giving their employees financial performance incentives in order to make them increase their efficiency.

4.2.4 Effects of Non-financial Performance Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State

The study sought to examine effect of non-financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State. To this effect, the respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

The result is shown in table 4.4.

Table 4.4 Effects of Non-financial Performance Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State

Effect of Non-financial Performance Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State	SD	D	U	A	SA
The non-financial performance incentives the employees in this bank enjoy, such as training, feedback to the employees, career development, recognition, employee participation and work environment are adequate.	4 (7.7%)	12 (23.1%)	10 (19.2%)	19 (36.5%)	7 (13.5%)
Before the employees in this bank started enjoying the non-financial performance incentives, their efficiency, in terms of speed and accuracy, did not increase.	8 (15.4%)	9 (17.3%)	25 (48.1%)	7 (13.5%)	3 (5.8%)
As soon as the employees in this bank started enjoying the non-financial performance incentives, their efficiency improved.	3 (5.8%)	6 (11.5%)	22 (42.3%)	16 (30.8%)	5 (9.6%)
Without the non-financial	6 (11.5%)	7 (13.5%)	23 (44.2%)	15 (28.8%)	1 (1.9%)

performance incentives employees of this bank currently enjoy, they will not be willing to increase their efficiency.					
Employees in this bank do their work with no errors due to the non-financial incentives they enjoy.	5 (9.6%)	11 (21.2%)	17 (32.7%)	15 (28.8%)	4 (7.7%)
This bank should ensure that its employees continue to enjoy non-financial performance incentives in order to make the employees increase their efficiency.	2 (3.8%)	4 (7.7%)	16 (30.8%)	25 (48.1%)	5 (9.6%)

Source: Author’s Fieldwork Computation Using SPSS 20.0, 2018

The findings shown in table 4.4 indicates 4 (7.7%) strongly disagree, 12 (23.1%) disagree, 10 (19.2%) undecided, 19 (36.5%) agree and 7 (13.5%) strongly agree that the non-financial incentives the employees in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA enjoy, such as training, feedback to the employees, career development, recognition, employee participation and work environment are adequate. Also, 8 (15.4%) strongly disagree, 9 (17.3%) disagree, 25 (48.1%) undecided, 7 (13.5%) agree and 3 (5.8%) strongly agree that before the employees in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA started enjoying the non-financial performance incentives, their efficiency, in terms of speed & accuracy, did not increase. Furthermore, of the 52 respondents, 3 (5.8%) strongly disagree, 6 (11.5%) disagree, 22 (42.3%) undecided, 16 (30.8%) agree and 5 (9.6%) strongly agree that as soon as the employees in Deposit Money Banks in

Dutsin-Ma LGA started enjoying the non-financial performance incentives, their efficiency improved. When asked whether the employees of the Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA will not be willing to increase their efficiency without the non-financial performance incentives they currently enjoy, 6 (11.5%) strongly disagree, 7 (13.5%) disagree, 23 (44.2%) undecided, 15 (28.8%) agree while 1 (1.9%) strongly agree. The table further shows 5 (9.6%) strongly disagree, 11 (21.2%) disagree, 17 (32.7%) undecided, 15 (28.8%) agree and 4 (7.7%) strongly agree that employees in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA do their work with no errors due to the non-financial incentives they enjoy. Finally, of the 52 respondents, 2 (3.8%) strongly disagree, 4 (7.7%) disagree, 16 (30.8%) undecided, 25 (48.1%) agree and 5 (9.6%) strongly agree that the Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA should ensure that their employees continue to enjoy non-financial performance incentives in order to make them increase their efficiency.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

The relevant hypotheses earlier formulated in the conduct of the study were tested in order to accept or reject the various assumptions. Chi-square (X^2) was adopted to test the validity of the hypotheses. Furthermore, all statistical tests were carried out as 95% level of confidence. The result of each tested hypothesis is presented below:

4.3.1 Hypothesis One

H₀: There are no significant differences among performance incentives used to encourage employees in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area.

H₁: There are significant differences among performance incentives used to encourage employees in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area.

Table 4.5 Chi-Squared (X^2) Test Showing the Result of Hypothesis One

STATEMENT	SD	D	U	A	SA	TOTAL
This bank provides its employees with a basic payment that is commensurate to their respective grade levels.	1	5	9	21	16	52
This bank pays its employees a proportion of its profit before interest and tax (PBIT) as a form of profit sharing.	5	6	17	16	8	52
When an employee meets up with or exceeds targets, this bank gives them some amount of money other than the basic pay as a form of gain sharing.	7	9	9	18	9	52
This bank provides benefits such as official car, official house, life assurance, private medical care and annual holiday entitlement to its employees.	0	7	9	16	20	52
This bank rewards its employees for using their own initiatives when they are faced with challenges as regards the task assigned to them.	4	8	17	18	5	52

This bank gives its employees special rewards in form of an all-expense-paid trip to a specific place of interest and tickets to sports events/cinemas.	3	11	17	14	7	52
This bank gives its employees feedback on how efficient they are with regard to the tasks assigned to them.	1	3	16	16	16	52
This bank gives due recognition such as employee of the month/year, "thank you", certificate of recognition and gift items to employees who efficiently do their work.	4	10	8	14	16	52
In this bank, employees participate in decisions regarding their job design and other decisions as they affect employees' work.	4	5	14	19	10	52
The working environment in this bank, such as supervisor's/branch manager's support is okay.	0	5	8	22	17	52
This bank gives its employees enough opportunity to develop their careers.	5	7	10	19	11	52

This bank gives its employees relevant trainings so that the employees can acquire necessary knowledge & skills required in carrying out the task assigned to them.	2	2	9	19	20	52
TOTAL	36	78	143	212	155	624

STATEMENT	SD	D	U	A	SA	TOTAL
This bank provides its employees with a basic payment that is commensurate to their respective grade levels.	e11	e12	e13	e14	e15	52
This bank pays its employees a proportion of its profit before interest and tax (PBIT) as a form of profit sharing.	e21	e22	e23	e24	e25	52
When an employee meets up with or exceeds targets, this bank gives them some amount of money other than the basic pay as a form of gain sharing.	e31	e32	e33	e34	e35	52
This bank provides benefits such as official car, official house, life	e41	e42	e43	e44	e45	52

assurance, private medical care and annual holiday entitlement to its employees.						
This bank rewards its employees for using their own initiatives when they are faced with challenges as regards the task assigned to them.	e51	e52	e53	e54	e55	52
This bank gives its employees special rewards in form of an all-expense-paid trip to a specific place of interest and tickets to sports events/cinemas.	e61	e62	e63	e64	e65	52
This bank gives its employees feedback on how efficient they are with regard to the tasks assigned to them.	e71	e72	e73	e74	e75	52
This bank gives due recognition such as employee of the month/year, "thank you", certificate of recognition and gift items to employees who efficiently do their work.	e81	e82	e83	e84	e85	52
In this bank, employees participate in decisions regarding their job design and other decisions as they affect	e91	e92	e93	e94	e95	52

employees' work.						
The working environment in this bank, such as supervisor's/branch manager's support is okay.	e101	e102	e103	e104	e105	52
This bank gives its employees enough opportunity to develop their careers.	e111	e112	e113	e114	e115	52
This bank gives its employees relevant trainings so that the employees can acquire necessary knowledge & skills required in carrying out the task assigned to them.	e121	e122	e123	e124	e125	52
TOTAL	36	78	143	212	155	624

Expected Frequencies:

$$e_{11} = \frac{52 \times 36}{624} = 3.00$$

$$e_{12} = \frac{52 \times 78}{624} = 6.50$$

$$e_{13} = \frac{52 \times 143}{624} = 11.92$$

$$e_{14} = \frac{52 \times 212}{624} = 17.67$$

$$e_{15} = \frac{52 \times 155}{624} = 12.92$$

$$e_{21} = \frac{52 \times 36}{624} = 3.00$$

$$e_{22} = \frac{52 \times 78}{624} = 6.50$$

$$e_{23} = \frac{52 \times 143}{624} = 11.92$$

$$e_{24} = \frac{52 \times 212}{624} = 17.67$$

$$e_{25} = \frac{52 \times 155}{624} = 12.92$$

$$e_{31} = \frac{52 \times 36}{624} = 3.00$$

$$e_{32} = \frac{52 \times 78}{624} = 6.50$$

$$e_{33} = \frac{52 \times 143}{624} = 11.92$$

$$e_{34} = \frac{52 \times 212}{624} = 17.67$$

$$e_{35} = \frac{52 \times 155}{624} = 12.92$$

$$e_{41} = \frac{52 \times 36}{624} = 3.00$$

$$e_{42} = \frac{52 \times 78}{624} = 6.50$$

$$e_{43} = \frac{52 \times 143}{624} = 11.92$$

$$\begin{aligned}
e44 &= \frac{52 \times 212}{624} = 17.67 & e45 &= \frac{52 \times 155}{624} = 12.92 & e51 &= \frac{52 \times 36}{624} = 3.00 \\
e52 &= \frac{52 \times 78}{624} = 6.50 & e53 &= \frac{52 \times 143}{624} = 11.92 & e54 &= \frac{52 \times 212}{624} = 17.67 \\
e55 &= \frac{52 \times 155}{624} = 12.92 & e61 &= \frac{52 \times 36}{624} = 3.00 & e62 &= \frac{52 \times 78}{624} = 6.50 \\
e63 &= \frac{52 \times 143}{624} = 11.92 & e64 &= \frac{52 \times 212}{624} = 17.67 & e65 &= \frac{52 \times 155}{624} = 12.92 \\
e71 &= \frac{52 \times 36}{624} = 3.00 & e72 &= \frac{52 \times 78}{624} = 6.50 & e73 &= \frac{52 \times 143}{624} = 11.92 \\
e74 &= \frac{52 \times 212}{624} = 17.67 & e75 &= \frac{52 \times 155}{624} = 12.92 & e81 &= \frac{52 \times 36}{624} = 3.00 \\
e82 &= \frac{52 \times 78}{624} = 6.50 & e83 &= \frac{52 \times 143}{624} = 11.92 & e84 &= \frac{52 \times 212}{624} = 17.67 \\
e85 &= \frac{52 \times 155}{624} = 12.92 & e91 &= \frac{52 \times 36}{624} = 3.00 & e92 &= \frac{52 \times 78}{624} = 6.50 \\
e93 &= \frac{52 \times 143}{624} = 11.92 & e94 &= \frac{52 \times 212}{624} = 17.67 & e95 &= \frac{52 \times 155}{624} = 12.92 \\
e101 &= \frac{52 \times 36}{624} = 3.00 & e102 &= \frac{52 \times 78}{624} = 6.50 & e103 &= \frac{52 \times 143}{624} = 11.92 \\
e104 &= \frac{52 \times 212}{624} = 17.67 & e105 &= \frac{52 \times 155}{624} = 12.92 & e111 &= \frac{52 \times 36}{624} = 3.00 \\
e112 &= \frac{52 \times 78}{624} = 6.50 & e113 &= \frac{52 \times 143}{624} = 11.92 & e114 &= \frac{52 \times 212}{624} = 17.67 \\
e115 &= \frac{52 \times 155}{624} = 12.92 & e121 &= \frac{52 \times 36}{624} = 3.00 & e122 &= \frac{52 \times 78}{624} = 6.50 \\
e123 &= \frac{52 \times 143}{624} = 11.92 & e124 &= \frac{52 \times 212}{624} = 17.67 & e125 &= \frac{52 \times 155}{624} = 12.92
\end{aligned}$$

Table 4.6 Computation of Chi-square Test Statistic for Hypothesis One

Fo	Fe	Fo – Fe	(Fo – Fe)²	$\frac{(Fo - Fe)^2}{Fe}$
1	3.00	-2.00	4.00	1.3333
5	6.50	-1.50	2.25	0.3462
9	11.92	-2.92	8.5264	0.7153

21	17.67	3.33	11.0889	0.6276
16	12.92	3.08	9.4864	0.7342
5	3.00	2.00	4.00	1.3333
6	6.50	-0.50	0.25	0.0385
17	11.92	5.08	25.8064	2.1650
16	17.67	-1.67	2.7889	0.1578
8	12.92	-4.92	24.2064	1.8736
7	3.00	4.00	16.00	5.3333
9	6.50	2.50	6.25	0.9615
9	11.92	-2.92	8.5264	0.7153
18	17.67	0.33	0.1089	0.0062
9	12.92	-3.92	15.3664	1.1893
0	3.00	-3.00	9.00	3.00
7	6.50	0.50	0.25	0.0385
9	11.92	-2.92	8.5264	0.7153
16	17.67	-1.67	2.7889	0.1578
20	12.92	7.08	50.1264	3.8798
4	3.00	1.00	1.00	0.3333
8	6.50	1.5	2.25	0.3462
17	11.92	5.08	25.8064	2.1650
18	17.67	0.33	0.1089	0.0062
5	12.92	-7.92	62.7264	4.8550
3	3.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

11	6.50	4.50	20.25	3.1154
17	11.92	5.08	25.8064	2.1650
14	17.67	-3.67	13.4689	0.7622
7	12.92	-5.92	35.0464	2.7126
1	3.00	-2.00	4.00	1.3333
3	6.50	-3.50	12.25	1.8846
16	11.92	4.08	16.6464	1.3965
16	17.67	-1.67	2.7889	0.1578
16	12.92	3.08	9.4864	0.7342
4	3.00	1.00	1.00	0.3333
10	6.50	3.5	12.25	1.8846
8	11.92	-3.92	15.3664	1.2891
14	17.67	-3.67	13.4689	0.7622
16	12.92	3.08	9.4864	0.7342
4	3.00	1.00	1.00	0.3333
5	6.50	-1.50	2.25	0.3462
14	11.92	2.08	4.3264	0.3630
19	17.67	1.33	1.7689	0.1001
10	12.92	-2.92	8.5264	0.6599
0	3.00	-3.00	9.00	3.00
5	6.50	-1.50	2.25	0.3462
8	11.92	-3.92	15.3664	1.2891
22	17.67	4.33	18.7489	1.0611

17	12.92	4.08	16.6464	1.2884
5	3.00	2.00	4.00	1.3333
7	6.50	0.50	0.25	0.0385
10	11.92	-1.92	3.6864	0.3093
19	17.67	1.33	1.7689	0.1001
11	12.92	-1.92	3.6864	0.2853
2	3.00	-1.00	1.00	0.3333
2	6.50	-4.50	20.25	3.1154
9	11.92	-2.92	8.5264	0.7153
19	17.67	1.33	1.7689	0.1001
20	12.92	7.08	50.1264	3.8798
				$\frac{\Sigma(F_o - F_e)^2}{F_e} = 71.29$

Decision Rule

Reject Null Hypothesis (H_0) if computed chi-squared is greater than the tabulated or critical value (i.e. $X^2 > X^2\alpha_{(r-1)(c-1)}$), otherwise accept H_0 .

$$df = (r - 1)(c - 1) = (12 - 1)(5 - 1) = (11)(4) = 44$$

$$X^2\alpha_{(r-1)(c-1)} = X^20.05_{(12-1)(5-1)} = X^20.05_{(11)(4)}$$

$$= X^20.05_{(44)} = \underline{60.48}$$

$$X^2 = \frac{\Sigma(F_o - F_e)^2}{F_e} = \underline{71.29}$$

Decision

Since the computed chi-squared (X^2) is greater than the critical value (i.e. $71.29 > 60.48$), then, there is no evidence to support the assumption that there are no significant differences among performance incentives used to encourage employees in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis and then conclude that there are significant differences among performance incentives used to encourage employees in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria.

4.3.2 Hypothesis Two

H₀: There are no significant effects of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area.

H₁: There are significant effects of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area.

Table 4.7 Chi-Squared (X^2) Test Showing the Result of Hypothesis Two

STATEMENT	SD	D	U	A	SA	TOTAL
The financial incentives my bank gives its employees, such as base pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits, initiative rewards and special rewards are adequate.	2	11	16	18	5	52
Before my bank gives the financial incentives, employee efficiency remains the same.	4	12	20	12	4	52

As soon as my bank gives its employees financial incentives, employee efficiency improves.	0	4	11	20	17	52
Without the financial incentives, employees in this bank are not willing to increase the speed at which they work.	6	7	22	12	5	52
Employees in this bank do their works with no errors because of the financial incentives given to them.	2	6	19	16	9	52
This bank should continue giving its employees financial performance incentives in order to make the employees increase their efficiency.	3	0	9	25	15	52
TOTAL	17	40	97	103	55	312

STATEMENT	SD	D	U	A	SA	TOTAL
The financial incentives my bank gives its employees, such as base pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits, initiative rewards and special rewards are adequate.	e11	e12	e13	e14	e15	52
Before my bank gives the financial incentives, employee efficiency remains	e21	e22	e23	e24	e25	52

the same.						
As soon as my bank gives its employees financial incentives, employee efficiency improves.	e31	e32	e33	e34	e35	52
Without the financial incentives, employees in this bank are not willing to increase the speed at which they work.	e41	e42	e43	e44	e45	52
Employees in this bank do their works with no errors because of the financial incentives given to them.	e51	e52	e53	e54	e55	52
This bank should continue giving its employees financial performance incentives in order to make the employees increase their efficiency.	e61	e62	e63	e64	e65	52
TOTAL	21	56	122	87	26	312

Expected Frequencies:

$$e_{11} = \frac{52 \times 17}{312} = 2.83$$

$$e_{12} = \frac{52 \times 40}{312} = 6.67$$

$$e_{13} = \frac{52 \times 97}{312} = 16.17$$

$$e_{14} = \frac{52 \times 103}{312} = 17.17$$

$$e_{15} = \frac{52 \times 55}{312} = 9.17$$

$$e_{21} = \frac{52 \times 17}{312} = 2.83$$

$$e_{22} = \frac{52 \times 40}{312} = 6.67$$

$$e_{23} = \frac{52 \times 97}{312} = 16.17$$

$$e_{24} = \frac{52 \times 103}{312} = 17.17$$

$$e_{25} = \frac{52 \times 55}{312} = 9.17$$

$$e_{31} = \frac{52 \times 17}{312} = 2.83$$

$$e_{32} = \frac{52 \times 40}{312} = 6.67$$

$$e_{33} = \frac{52 \times 97}{312} = 16.17$$

$$e_{34} = \frac{52 \times 103}{312} = 17.17$$

$$e_{35} = \frac{52 \times 55}{312} = 9.17$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 e41 &= \frac{52 \times 17}{312} = 2.83 & e42 &= \frac{52 \times 40}{312} = 6.67 & e43 &= \frac{52 \times 97}{312} = 16.17 \\
 e44 &= \frac{52 \times 103}{312} = 17.17 & e45 &= \frac{52 \times 55}{312} = 9.17 & e51 &= \frac{52 \times 17}{312} = 2.83 \\
 e52 &= \frac{52 \times 40}{312} = 6.67 & e53 &= \frac{52 \times 97}{312} = 16.17 & e54 &= \frac{52 \times 103}{312} = 17.17 \\
 e55 &= \frac{52 \times 55}{312} = 9.17 & e61 &= \frac{52 \times 17}{312} = 2.83 & e62 &= \frac{52 \times 40}{312} = 6.67 \\
 e63 &= \frac{52 \times 97}{312} = 16.17 & e64 &= \frac{52 \times 103}{312} = 17.17 & e65 &= \frac{52 \times 55}{312} = 9.17
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 4.8 Computation of Chi-square Test Statistic for Hypothesis Two

Fo	Fe	Fo – Fe	(Fo – Fe)²	$\frac{(Fo - Fe)^2}{Fe}$
2	2.83	- 0.83	0.6889	0.2434
11	6.67	4.33	18.7489	2.8109
16	16.17	- 0.17	0.0289	0.0018
18	17.17	0.83	0.6889	0.0401
5	9.17	- 4.17	17.3889	1.8963
4	2.83	1.17	1.3689	0.4837
12	6.67	5.33	28.4089	4.2592
20	16.17	3.83	14.6689	0.9072
12	17.17	- 5.17	26.7289	1.5567
4	9.17	- 5.17	26.7289	2.9148
0	2.83	- 2.83	8.0089	2.8300
4	6.67	- 2.67	7.1289	1.0688
11	16.17	- 5.17	26.7289	1.6530
20	17.17	2.83	8.0089	0.4664

17	9.17	7.83	61.3089	6.6858
6	2.83	3.17	10.0489	3.5508
7	6.67	0.33	0.1089	0.0163
22	16.17	5.83	33.9889	2.1020
12	17.17	- 5.17	26.7289	1.5567
5	9.17	- 4.17	17.3889	1.8963
2	2.83	- 0.83	0.6889	0.2434
6	6.67	- 0.67	0.4489	0.0673
19	16.17	2.83	8.0089	0.4953
16	17.17	- 1.17	1.3689	0.0797
9	9.17	- 0.17	0.0289	0.0032
3	2.83	0.17	0.0289	0.0102
0	6.67	- 6.67	44.4889	6.6700
9	16.17	- 7.17	51.4089	3.1793
25	17.17	7.83	61.3089	3.5707
15	9.17	5.83	33.9889	3.7065
				$\frac{\Sigma(F_o - F_e)^2}{F_e} = \underline{\underline{54.97}}$

Decision Rule

Reject Null Hypothesis (H_0) if computed chi-squared is greater than the tabulated or critical value (i.e. $X^2 > X^2_{\alpha(r-1)(c-1)}$), otherwise accept H_0 .

$$df = (r - 1)(c - 1) = (6 - 1)(5 - 1) = (5)(4) = 20$$

$$X^2_{\alpha(r-1)(c-1)} = X^2_{0.05(6-1)(5-1)} = X^2_{0.05(5)(4)}$$

$$= X^2_{0.05(20)} = \underline{31.41}$$

$$X^2 = \frac{\Sigma(F_o - F_e)^2}{F_e} = \underline{54.97}$$

Decision

Since the computed chi-squared (X^2) is greater than the critical value (i.e. $54.97 > 31.41$), then, there is no evidence to support the assumption that there are no significant effects of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis and then conclude that there are significant effects of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria.

4.3.3 Hypothesis Three

H₀: There are no significant effects of non-financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area.

H₁: There are significant effects of non-financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area.

Table 4.9 Chi-Squared (X^2) Test Showing the Result of Hypothesis Three

Effect of Non-financial Performance Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State	SD	D	U	A	SA	TOTAL
The non-financial performance incentives the employees in this bank	4	12	10	19	7	52

enjoy, such as training, feedback to the employees, career development, recognition, employee participation and work environment are adequate.						
Before the employees in this bank started enjoying the non-financial performance incentives, their efficiency, in terms of speed & accuracy, did not increase.	8	9	25	7	3	52
As soon as the employees in this bank started enjoying the non-financial performance incentives, their efficiency improved.	3	6	22	16	5	52
Without the non-financial performance incentives employees of this bank currently enjoy, they will not be willing to increase their efficiency.	6	7	23	15	1	52
Employees in this bank do their work with no errors due to the non-financial incentives they enjoy.	5	11	17	15	4	52
This bank should ensure that its employees continue to enjoy non-financial performance incentives in	2	4	16	25	5	52

order to make the employees increase their efficiency.						
TOTAL	28	49	113	97	25	312

Effect of Non-financial Performance	SD	D	U	A	SA	TOTAL
Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State						
The non-financial performance incentives the employees in this bank enjoy, such as training, feedback to the employees, career development, recognition, employee participation and work environment are adequate.	e11	e12	e13	e14	e15	52
Before the employees in this bank started enjoying the non-financial performance incentives, their efficiency, in terms of speed & accuracy, did not increase.	e21	e22	e23	e24	e25	52
As soon as the employees in this bank started enjoying the non-financial performance incentives, their efficiency improved.	e31	e32	e33	e34	e35	52

Without the non-financial performance incentives employees of this bank currently enjoy, they will not be willing to increase their efficiency.	e41	e42	e43	e44	e45	52
Employees in this bank do their work with no errors due to the non-financial incentives they enjoy.	e51	e52	e53	e54	e55	52
This bank should ensure that its employees continue to enjoy non-financial performance incentives in order to make the employees increase their efficiency.	e61	e62	e63	e64	e65	52
TOTAL	28	49	113	97	25	312

Expected Frequencies:

$$e_{11} = \frac{52 \times 28}{312} = 4.67$$

$$e_{12} = \frac{52 \times 49}{312} = 8.17$$

$$e_{13} = \frac{52 \times 113}{312} = 18.83$$

$$e_{14} = \frac{52 \times 97}{312} = 16.17$$

$$e_{15} = \frac{52 \times 25}{312} = 4.17$$

$$e_{21} = \frac{52 \times 28}{312} = 4.67$$

$$e_{22} = \frac{52 \times 49}{312} = 8.17$$

$$e_{23} = \frac{52 \times 113}{312} = 18.83$$

$$e_{24} = \frac{52 \times 97}{312} = 16.17$$

$$e_{25} = \frac{52 \times 25}{312} = 4.17$$

$$e_{31} = \frac{52 \times 28}{312} = 4.67$$

$$e_{32} = \frac{52 \times 49}{312} = 8.17$$

$$e_{33} = \frac{52 \times 113}{312} = 18.83$$

$$e_{34} = \frac{52 \times 97}{312} = 16.17$$

$$e_{35} = \frac{52 \times 25}{312} = 4.17$$

$e_{41} =$

$$\frac{52 \times 28}{312} = 4.67$$

$$e_{42} = \frac{52 \times 49}{312} = 8.17$$

$$e_{43} = \frac{52 \times 113}{312} = 18.83$$

$$e_{44} = \frac{52 \times 97}{312} = 16.17$$

$$e_{45} = \frac{52 \times 25}{312} = 4.17$$

$$e_{51} = \frac{52 \times 28}{312} = 4.67$$

$$e52 = \frac{52 \times 49}{312} = 8.17 \quad e53 = \frac{52 \times 113}{312} = 18.83 \quad e54 = \frac{52 \times 97}{312} = 16.17$$

$$e55 = \frac{52 \times 25}{312} = 4.17 \quad e61 = \frac{52 \times 28}{312} = 4.67 \quad e62 = \frac{52 \times 49}{312} = 8.17$$

$$e63 = \frac{52 \times 113}{312} = 18.83 \quad e64 = \frac{52 \times 97}{312} = 16.17 \quad e65 = \frac{52 \times 25}{312} = 4.17$$

Table 4.10 Computation of Chi-square Test Statistic for Hypothesis Three

Fo	Fe	Fo - Fe	(Fo - Fe)²	$\frac{(Fo - Fe)^2}{Fe}$
4	4.67	- 0.67	0.4489	0.0961
12	8.17	3.83	14.6689	1.7955
10	18.83	- 8.83	77.9689	4.1407
19	16.17	2.83	8.0089	0.4953
7	4.17	2.83	8.0089	1.9206
8	4.67	3.33	11.0889	2.6592
9	8.17	0.83	0.6889	0.0843
25	18.83	6.17	38.0689	2.0217
7	16.17	- 9.17	84.0889	5.2003
3	4.17	- 1.17	14.3889	3.4506
3	4.67	- 1.67	18.8089	4.0276
6	8.17	- 2.17	4.7089	0.5764
22	18.83	3.17	10.0489	0.5337
16	16.17	- 0.17	0.0289	0.0018
5	4.17	0.83	0.6889	0.1652
6	4.67	1.33	1.7689	0.3788

7	8.17	- 1.17	1.3689	0.1676
23	18.83	4.17	17.3889	0.9235
15	16.17	- 1.17	1.3689	0.0847
1	4.17	- 3.17	10.0489	2.4098
5	4.67	0.33	0.1089	0.0233
11	8.17	2.83	8.0089	0.9803
17	18.83	- 1.83	3.3489	0.1778
15	16.17	- 1.17	1.3689	0.0847
4	4.17	- 0.17	0.0289	0.0069
2	4.67	- 2.67	7.1289	1.5265
4	8.17	- 4.17	17.3889	2.1284
16	18.83	- 2.83	8.0089	0.4253
25	16.17	8.83	77.9689	4.8218
5	4.17	0.83	0.6889	0.1652
				$\frac{\Sigma(\text{Fo}-\text{Fe})^2}{\text{Fe}} = \underline{41.47}$

Decision Rule

Reject Null Hypothesis (H_0) if computed chi-squared is greater than the tabulated or critical value (i.e. $X^2 > X^2\alpha_{(r-1)(c-1)}$), otherwise accept H_0 .

$$df = (r - 1)(c - 1) = (6 - 1)(5 - 1) = (5)(4) = 20$$

$$X^2\alpha_{(r-1)(c-1)} = X^20.05_{(6-1)(5-1)} = X^20.05_{(5)(4)}$$

$$= X^20.05_{(20)} = \underline{31.41}$$

$$X^2 = \frac{\Sigma(F_o - F_e)^2}{F_e} = \underline{\underline{41.47}}$$

Decision

Since the computed chi-squared (X^2) is greater than the critical value (i.e. $41.47 > 31.41$), then, there is no evidence to support the assumption that there are no significant effects of non-financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternate hypothesis (H_1) and then conclude that there are significant effects of non-financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria.

4.4 Discussion of Research Findings

The study investigated the effect of performance incentives on employee efficiency with specific reference to the Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria and drew from previous related studies. Consequently, following significant results were found.

Firstly, the results showed that basic pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits (such as official car, official house, life assurance, private medical care and annual holiday entitlement), initiative rewards, special rewards (such as an all-expense-paid trip to a specific place of interest and tickets to sports events/cinemas), feedback to employees, employee recognition, employee participation, better working environment, career development opportunities and training were all adopted by the Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria to encourage employees. This finding supports the finding of Oburu and Atambo (2016) who also found that there are significant differences in the performance incentives used in the microfinance industry to improve efficiency, which also promoted

employee efficiency and that they were effective ways of compensating employees for better performance in the microfinance industry. Furthermore, the finding is in line with the finding of Huttu (2010) who has also found that incentives have significant differences on employee performance, although, there is not much variation in the importance of different incentives.

Furthermore, the results revealed that the financial incentives the Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria give their employees (such as base pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits, initiative rewards and special rewards) were adequate. But, it was uncertain if employee efficiency remains the same before the banks give their employees financial incentives. In like manner, it was uncertain if employee will be willing to increase the speed at which they work without the financial incentives given them. However, as soon as these banks give their employees financial incentives, employee efficiency improves and employees do their works with no errors owing to the financial incentives given them while they would also want the banks to continue giving them financial performance incentives in order to make them increase their efficiency. This finding is in line with the finding of Al-Nsour (2012) who found that there is a significant relationship between financial & moral incentives and performance in the Jordanian universities. Furthermore, the finding supports the finding of Huttu (2010) who has also found that monetary incentives are important to employees as they improve employee performance.

Finally, the results further showed that the non-financial performance incentives (such as training, feedback to employees, career development, recognition, employees' participation and better work environment) the employees in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria enjoy are adequate. But, it was uncertain if employee efficiency, in terms of speed and accuracy, did not increase before employees started

enjoying the non-financial performance incentives given them. In like manner, it was uncertain if employee efficiency improved as soon as the employees started enjoying the non-financial performance incentives given them or whether they will not be willing to increase their efficiency without the non-financial performance incentives they currently enjoy. However, employees in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria do their work with no errors due to the non-financial incentives they enjoy and would like the banks to ensure that employees continue to enjoy non-financial performance incentives in order to make them increase their efficiency. This finding supports the finding of Oburu and Atambo (2016) who have found that non-financial incentives promoted employee efficiency and that they were effective ways of compensating employees for better performance in the microfinance industry. Furthermore, the finding is in line with the finding of Huttu (2010) who has also found that non-financial incentives improved performance and can be more cost-effective than financial incentives because non-financial incentives do not include any direct costs. The finding also supports the findings of previous researches that non-financial incentives have improved performance by several per cent (e.g. Brown, 1996; Cotton, Vollrath, Froggatt, & Lengnick-Hall, 1988; Deci, Koestner, & Ryan, 1999; Kluger & DeNisi, 1996; Locke, Feren, McCaleb, & Shaw, 1980; Rynes, Gerhart, & Parks, 2005; Stajkovic & Luthans, 2001). Hence, non-financial incentives can be considered as playing important roles in increasing performance, especially, in the long run (Huttu, 2010).

Conclusively, on the bases of the formulated hypotheses, all the null hypotheses of the study were rejected, thereby, giving room for the acceptance of all the alternate hypotheses because the calculated values were all greater than the critical values at 5% level of significance using chi-squared (X^2) test.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary of Findings

The objective of the study was to determine the effect of performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area (LGA) of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria. The study was guided by the following research questions: What are the performance incentives used in DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA to encourage employees? What are the effects of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA? What are the effects of nonfinancial performance incentives on employee efficiency in DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA? The researcher reviewed a number of previous related studies and rooted the study in such motivational theories as Victor H. Vroom's Expectancy Theory and Stacy J. Adam's Equity Theory. The study adopted the cross-sectional survey research design, which is descriptive in nature. The population of the study were the employees of the DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina State (vis-à-vis First Bank Nigeria Ltd., United Bank for Africa PLC and Unity Bank PLC), which totalled sixty (60) employees and out of which a sample of 52 respondents was drawn using the proportional stratum allocation technique and the simple random sampling technique. The primary data was collected through structured questionnaire. Data collected was analysed through descriptive and inferential statistics using Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 20 (SPSS v.20).

The findings on performance incentives adopted by DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA to encourage employees showed that training ranked 1st with a mean of 4.02 and a standard deviation of 1.038; better working environment ranked 2nd with a mean of 3.98 and a standard deviation of 0.939; benefits ranked 3rd with a mean of 3.94 and a standard deviation of 1.056; base pay ranked 4th

with a mean of 3.88 and a standard deviation of 1.022; feedback ranked 5th with a mean of 3.83 and a standard deviation of 1.004; recognition ranked 6th with a mean of 3.54 and a standard deviation of 1.320; participation ranked 7th with a mean of 3.50 and a standard deviation of 1.146; career development ranked 8th with a mean of 3.46 and a standard deviation of 1.244; profit sharing ranked 9th with a mean of 3.31 and a standard deviation of 1.164; gain sharing ranked 10th with a mean of 3.25 and a standard deviation of 1.312; initiative rewards ranked 11th with a mean of 3.23 and a standard deviation of 1.078; special rewards ranked 12th with a mean of 3.21 and a standard deviation of 1.109 and there are significant differences among the performance incentives used. This finding is in line with the finding of Oburu and Atambo (2016) who also found that there are significant differences in the performance incentives used in the microfinance industry to improve efficiency, which also promoted employee efficiency and that they were effective ways of compensating employees for better performance in the microfinance industry. Furthermore, the finding supports the finding of Huttu (2010) who has also found that incentives have significant differences on employee performance, although, there is not much variation in the importance of different incentives.

The findings on effects of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA showed that there are significant effects of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA. This finding is in line with the finding of Al-Nsour (2012) who found that there is a significant relationship between financial & moral incentives and performance in the Jordanian universities. Furthermore, the finding supports the finding of Huttu (2010) who has also found that monetary incentives are important to employees as they improve employee performance.

The findings on effects of non-financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA showed that there are significant effects of non-financial performance incentives on employee efficiency in DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA. This finding supports the finding of Oburu and Atambo (2016) who also found that non-financial incentives promoted employee efficiency and that they were effective ways of compensating employees for better performance in the microfinance industry. Furthermore, the finding is in line with the finding of Huttu (2010) who has also found that non-financial incentives improved performance and can be more cost-effective than financial incentives because non-financial incentives do not include any direct costs. The finding also supports the findings of previous researches that non-financial incentives have improved performance by several per cent (e.g. Brown, 1996; Cotton, Vollrath, Froggatt, & Lengnick-Hall, 1988; Deci, Koestner, & Ryan, 1999; Kluger & DeNisi, 1996; Locke, Feren, McCaleb, & Shaw, 1980; Rynes, Gerhart, & Parks, 2005; Stajkovic & Luthans, 2001). Hence, nonfinancial incentives can be considered as playing important roles in increasing performance, especially, in the long run (Huttu, 2010).

5.2 Conclusion

From the findings of this study, the DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA encourage employees through performance incentives and there are positive significant differences among the performance incentives used (*vis-à-vis* training, better working environment, benefits, base pay, feedback, recognition, participation, career development, profit sharing, gain sharing, initiative rewards and special rewards); financial performance incentives have positive significant effects on employee efficiency in DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA and nonfinancial performance incentives have positive significant effects on employee efficiency in DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA. Hence, I have reached the conclusion, based on the objective of this study, that there is a positive significant effect of

performance incentives on employee efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Northwest-Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

On the bases of the findings of this study, following recommendations were offered:

1. Management should increase the level of performance incentives they give their employees or as enjoyed by their employees (in the following order: special rewards, initiative rewards, gain sharing, profit sharing, career development, participation, recognition, feedback, base pay, benefits, better working environment and training) in order to increase and sustain their employees' levels of efficiency.
2. Management should continue to give their employees financial incentives (such as base pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits, initiative rewards and special rewards) in order to increase and sustain their employees' efficiency, make them be willing to increase the speed at which they work, and for them to continue to do their work with no errors.
3. Management should continue to allow their employees enjoy non-financial incentives (such as training, feedback to employees, career development, recognition, employee participation and better work environment) in order that employee efficiency can continue to improve and so that employees may continue to do their work with no errors.

5.4 Limitations of the Study

This study has revealed some limitations. For instance, out of the twenty-two DMBs licensed to operate, in Nigeria, only three of them (First Bank Nigeria Ltd., United Bank for Africa PLC and Unity Bank PLC) operate in Dutsin-Ma LGA. Hence, the findings of this study may not be generalized to all DMBs in Nigeria. The use of Chi-squared (X^2), which is a non-parametric statistical tool, is another limitation. Inadequate relevant literature was another shortcoming.

5.5 Contributions to Knowledge

This study has contributed the following to the body of knowledge:

1. Development of a model on the effect of performance incentives on employee efficiency.
2. Development of performance incentives construct through adaptation.
3. Giving an insight into the study of the relationship between performance incentives and employee efficiency.
4. The laying of a research foundation, which other researchers can build on with regard to performance incentives and employee efficiency.

5.6 Suggestions for further Studies

The study provided a direction for future research as the future research can also be conducted to examine areas such as: effect of performance incentives on employee efficiency in a non-service sector, using the same variables as those of this study, so that results can be comparable; effect of financial performance incentives on employee efficiency, using the same variables as those of this study, so that results can be comparable; effect of non-financial performance incentives on employee efficiency, using the same variables as those of this study, so that results can be comparable; impact of performance incentives on employee efficiency, using the same variables as those of this study, in order to know whether it is performance incentives that lead to employee efficiency or vice versa; a comparative study between the level of financial performance incentives and non-financial performance incentives provided to employees in the DMBs in Dutsin-Ma LGA to raise employee efficiency; effect of performance incentives on non-financial performance of organization with a mediating role of employee efficiency, using the same variables as those of this study, so that results can be comparable.

References

- Adams, S. J. (1966). Inequity in social exchange. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, 2, 267-299.
- Akerele, A. (1991). Role of Labour in Productivity. *Nigeria Journal of Industrial Relation*, 5, 50-58.
- Al-Aydi, K. (2000). Impact of incentives on performance in public firms of cotton industry in Iraq: A field study (Unpublished master's thesis). *Al al-Bayt University*, [Online] Retrieved from: http://web2.aabu.edu.jo/thesis_site/thes_dtl.jsp?thes_no=1811.
- Aldubekhi, I. (1991). *Incentives and Rewards Assessment in the Saudi Customs as a mean to Curb Smuggling*. Riyadh: Institute of Public Administration.
- Al-Harthi, D. (1999). Raising the Efficiency of Workers and Relationship with Financial and Moral Incentives: Case study on the Civil Defense Personnel in Riyadh. (Unpublished master's thesis) *Naif Arab Academy for Security Sciences*, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.
- Al-Nsour, M. (2012). Relationship between incentives and organizational performance for employees in the Jordanian universities. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7 (1), 78-89.
- Armstrong, M. (2001). *Human resource management practice: Handbook* (8th ed.). London: Kogan Page Ltd.
- Awan, A. G., & Tahir, T. M. (2015). Impact of working environment on employee's productivity: A case study of Banks and Insurance Companies in Pakistan. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7 (1), 329-345.
- Bari, N., Arif, U., & Shaib, A. (2013). Impact of non-financial rewards on employee attitude & performance in the workplace: A case study of Business Institutes of Karachi. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 4 (7), 2554-2559.
- Brimah, A. N. (2018). Job enrichment. *Unpublished lecture notes on Management Information System (BSM418)*, Federal University, Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State, Nigeria, 1-10.
- Brown, S. (1996). A meta-analysis and review of organizational research on job involvement.

- Psychological bulletin*, 120 (2), 235-255.
- Corby, S., White, G., & Stanworth, C. (2005). No news is good news? Evaluating new pay systems. *The Human Resource Management Journal*, 15 (1), 4-24.
- Dessler, G. (2005). *Human Resource Management* (10th Edition ed.). New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Dessler, G. (2008). Pay for Performance and Financial Incentives. In G. Dessler, *Human Resource Management* (11th Edition ed., pp. 1-14). India: Prentice Hall Inc.
- Drucker, P. (1974). *Management, Tasks, Responsibilities, Practices*. New York: Harper & Row.
- Dzuaranin, S. (2012). The effect of tangible and intangible noncash rewards on performance and satisfaction in production setting. *Management Accounting Quarterly*, 13 (4).
- Eposito, E. (2015, December 9). *Blog: Smartsheet Inc.* Retrieved May 21, 2018, from Smartsheet Inc. Website: <https://www.smartsheet.com/blog/how-calculate-productivity-all-levels-organization-employee-and-software>
- Everard, K. E., & Burrow, J. L. (2001). *Business Principles & Management*. Mason, Ohio: South-Western Educational Publishing.
- Fandom. (2017, April 2). *Employee characteristic: employee efficiency*. Retrieved May 3, 2018, from Fandom Website: http://psychology.wikia.com/wiki/Employee_efficiency
- Flippo, E. (1984). *Personnel Management* (6th Edition ed.). Singapore: McGraw-Hill International.
- Ghemawat, P., & Ricart, J. (1993). The Organizational Tension between Static and Dynamic Efficiency. *Strategic Management Journal*, 1-23.
- Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., & Black, W. (1998). *Multivariate Data Analysis* (5th ed.). New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
- Hicks, A. (2017, March 10). *Blog: Top 10 Ways to Improve Employee Efficiency*. Retrieved May 3, 2018, from Zenefits Website: <https://www.zenefits.com/blog/top-10-ways-to-improve-employee-efficiency>

- Hughes, J. (2007, July 2). *Office design is key to employee productivity*. Retrieved August 17, 2018, from Hughes Marino Website: <http://hughesmarino.com/san-diego/blog/2007/07/02/office-design-is-key-to-employee-productivity/>
- Huttu, E. (2010). The Effects of Incentives on Performance and Job Satisfaction: A literature review & interview research. *Tampere University of Technology*, 5-48.
- Khattak, M. A., Bashir, F., & Qureshi, T. M. (2010). Training & Development paradigm, and its contribution in economic uplift of the country: A case of Pakistan. *Conference Paper 12th International Business Research Conference*, (pp. 1-16). Pakistan.
- Kluger, A., & DeNisi, A. (1996). The Effects of Feedback Interventions on Performance: A Historical Review, a Meta-Analysis, and a Preliminary Feedback Intervention Theory. *Psychological Bulletin*, 119 (2), 254-284.
- Kurfi, A. K. (2013). *Human Resource Management*. Kano: Benchmark Publishers Limited.
- Love, A. (1991). *Internal Evaluation: Building Organizations from Within*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications.
- Makad, S. (2015, December 28). *Blogs: 5 Ways to Improve Your Employee Efficiency*. Retrieved April 30, 2018, from MyCustomer Website: <https://www.mycustomer.com/community/blogs/sammakad/5-ways-to-improve-your-employee-efficiency>
- Malhotra, M. (2017, March 15). *SlideShare.net*. Retrieved March 3, 2018, from SlideShare Website : https://www.slideshare.net/ravneetubs/incentives-and-performance-based-pay?qid=2ac62f6f-4097-4477-9c09-a04c75c29297&v=&b=&from_search=10
- Mugenda, O., & Mugenda, A. (2003). *Research Methods, Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches*. Nairobi, Kenya: African Centre for Technology Studies Press.
- Mukundi, N. E. (2016). Determinants of Employee Productivity in Private Limited Companies in Kenya: A Case Study of Equitorial Nut Processors Ltd. (Unpublished Master's Thesis). *Chandaria School of Business*, 1-100.

- Murphy, C., Cross, C., & McGuire, D. (2006). The motivation of nurses to participate in continuing professional education in Ireland. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 6 (5), 365-384.
- Ndetei, D., Ongecha, F., Mutiso, V., Kuria, M., Khasakhala, L., & Kokonya, D. (2007). The Challenges of Human Resources in mental Health in Kenya. *South Africa Psychiatry Review*, 10, 33-36.
- Nelson, D., & Quick, J. (2003). *Organizational Behaviour: Foundation, Realities and Challenges* (4th ed.). Australia: Thomson South-Western.
- Nigeria Institute of Management. (n.d.). *Management Principles & Techniques*. Nigeria: NIM.
- Nizamudheen. (2017, November 21). *Seven Traits of an Efficient Employee*. Retrieved April 30, 2018, from Output Time Website: <http://www.outputtime.com/seven-traits-of-an-efficient-employee/>
- Noordzij, L. (2013, July 4). *Knowledge: What is employee efficiency?* Retrieved May 3, 2018, from Effactory Website: <https://www.effactory.com/knowledge/themes/what-is-employee-efficiency>
- Oburu, L. N., & Atambo, W. N. (2016). The effect of non-financial compensation on employee performance of micro-finance institutions: A case of Wakenya Pamoja Sacco, Kisii County, Kenya. *Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research (IJIR)*, 2 (6), 103-126.
- Okwudili, B. E. (2015). Effect of Non-Monetary Rewards on Productivity of Employees Among Selected Government Parastatals In Abia State, Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 17 (2), 6-11.
- Orodho, J. (2009). *Elements of Education and Social Science Research Methods* (2nd ed.). Maseno, Kenya: Kanezja Publishers.
- Perry, J., Mesch, D., & Paarlberg, L. (2006). Motivating Employees in a New Governance Era: the Performance Paradigm Revisited. *Public Administration Review*, 66, 505-514.
- Petresca, A., & Simon, R. (2008). Human Resource Management Practices and Worker Job

- Satisfaction. *International Journal of Man Power*, 11 (7), 651-667.
- Rajendran, M. A., Mosisa, K. M., & Nedelea, A. (2017). Effects of non-monetary benefits on employee performance (A case of Bako Agricultural Research Center, Western Shoa, Ethiopia). *Ecoforum*, 6 (2)(11).
- Roelofsen, R. P. (2002). The impact of office environments on employee performance: The design of the workplace as a strategy for productivity enhancement. *Journal of Facilities Management; ABI/INFORM Global*, 1 (3), 247-264.
- Roscoe, J. (2002). Continuing professional development in higher education. *Human Resource Development International*, 5 (1), 3-9.
- Schermerhorn, J. R., Davidson, P., Factor, A., Poole, D., Woods, P., Simon, A., et al. (2017). *Management* (6th Asia-Pacific Edition ed.). Milton: Wiley.
- Shah, J., Higgins, T. E., & Friedman, R. S. (1998). Performance incentives and means: How regulatory focus influences goal attainment. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 74 (2), 285-293.
- Shaw, I. (2012). The Positive Contributions of Quantitative Methodology to Social Work Research: A View from the Side lines. *Research on Social Work Practice*, 22 (2), 129-134.
- Srivastava, A. e. (2001). Money and subjective well-being: it's not the money, it's the motives. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 80, 959-971.
- Stajkovic, A., & Luthans, F. (2001). Differential effects of incentive motivators on work performance. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 44 (3), 580-590.
- TaskManagementGuide. (2018). *What is employee efficiency*. Retrieved August 9, 2018, from TaskManagementGuide Website: <http://www.taskmanagementguide.com/glossary/what-is-employee-efficiency-.php>
- Taylor, M. (2017, February 10). *How to improve employee efficiency*. Retrieved April 30, 2018, from HRZone Website: <https://www.hrzone.com/community/blogs/mark-taylor/how-to-improve-employee-efficiency-0>

- Vroom, V. H. (1964). *Work and motivation*. New York: Wiley.
- Waqar, A., Sana, R., Kashif, A., & Ahson, H. (2018). Measuring the non-financial rewards in escalating employees job satisfaction: a study of private companies in Pakistan. *Asia Pacific Journal of Advanced Business and Social Studies*, 4 (1), 108-116.
- Woodruffe, C. (2006). The crucial importance of employee engagement. *Human Resource Management International Digest*, 14 (1), 3-5.
- Yamane, T. (1967). *Elementary sampling theory*. Prentice-Hall, New Jersey, United States: Englewoods Cliffs.

Appendix

Questionnaire

Federal University, Dutsin-Ma,
P.M.B. 5001,
Katsina,
Katsina State.

Dear respondent,

REQUEST TO FILL IN QUESTIONNAIRE

I am an undergraduate student of the Department of Business Management, Faculty of Management Sciences of the above-named Institution who is conducting a research on the topic: *Effect of Performance Incentives on Employee Efficiency in Deposit Money Banks in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area* in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of Bachelor of Science (BSc.) Degree in Business Management.

This questionnaire seeks to collect data related to the effect of performance incentives on employee efficiency as noted above. Hence, your sincere and objective response in filling in the questionnaire will be highly appreciated. All responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality and will only be used for the purpose of this study.

Thank you for your anticipated cooperation.

Yours faithfully,

A small rectangular box containing a handwritten signature and the date '27/08/18'.

Awotidebe, Samuel Olufemi

(Researcher)

SECTION A: Individual Bio-data (Tick [✓] as appropriate)

1. Gender:
Male []
Female []
2. Age Group (in years):
20 – 25 []
26 – 30 []
31 – 35 []
36 – 40 []
41 and above []
3. Highest Qualification:
O' Level []
OND/NCE []
HND/Bachelor's Degree []
MBA []
Master's Degree []
PhD []
4. Highest Professional Qualification:
Please, specify: _____
5. Employment Status:
Permanent Staff []
Casual Staff []
Contract Staff []
6. Total Years of Working Experience as a Bank Staff:
Below 1 year []
1 – 5 Years []
6 – 10 Years []
11 – 20 Years []
Above 20 Years []

7. Length of Service in this Bank:

Below 1 year []

1 – 2 Years []

3 – 5 Years []

6 – 10 Years []

11 – 15 Years []

Above 15 Years []

8. Monthly Net Pay (₦):

Below 20,000 []

20,001 – 40,000 []

40,001 – 60,000 []

60,001 – 80,000 []

80,001 – 100,000 []

Above 100,000 []

SECTION B

This section is divided into three parts. The purpose of this section is to know the performance incentives Deposit Money Banks (DMB's) in Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area (LGA) adopt to encourage employees and the effects of these performance incentives on employee efficiency. Please, read the statements in each part carefully and decide how you feel about them before making a selection. Kindly indicate the extent to which you agree/disagree with each statement by *ticking* [✓] the appropriate box, which has the following scales:

1 = Strongly Disagree	2 = Disagree	3 = Uncertain	4 = Agree	5 = Strongly Agree
-----------------------	--------------	---------------	-----------	--------------------

PART 1: Performance Incentives DMB's in Dutsin-Ma LGA adopt to Encourage Employees

S/N	Performance Incentives (PI) Adopted	1	2	3	4	5
1.	This bank provides its employees with a basic payment that is commensurate to their respective grade levels.					
2.	This bank pays its employees a proportion of its profit before interest and tax (PBIT) as a form of profit sharing.					

3.	When an employee meets up with or exceeds targets, this bank gives them some amount of money other than the basic pay as a form of gain sharing.					
4.	This bank provides benefits such as official car, official house, life assurance, private medical care and annual holiday entitlement to its employees.					
5.	This bank rewards its employees for using their own initiatives when they are faced with challenges as regards the task assigned to them.					
6.	This bank gives its employees special rewards in form of an all-expense-paid trip to a specific place of interest and tickets to sports events/cinemas.					
7.	This bank gives its employees feedback on how efficient they are with regard to the tasks assigned to them.					
8.	This bank gives due recognition such as employee of the month/year, "thank you", certificate of recognition and gift items to employees who efficiently do their work.					
9.	In this bank, employees participate in decisions regarding their job design and other decisions as they affect employees' work.					
10.	The working environment in this bank, such as supervisor's/branch manager's support is okay.					
11.	This bank gives its employees enough opportunity to develop their careers.					
12.	This bank gives its employees relevant trainings so that the employees can acquire necessary knowledge & skills required in carrying out the task assigned to them.					

PART 2: Effect of Financial Performance Incentives (FPI) on Employee Efficiency in DMB's in Dutsin-Ma LGA

S/N	Effect of FPI on Employee Efficiency	1	2	3	4	5
1.	The financial incentives my bank gives its employees, such as base pay, profit sharing, gain sharing, benefits, initiative rewards and special rewards are adequate.					
2.	Before my bank gives the financial incentives, employee efficiency remains the same.					
3.	As soon as my bank gives its employees financial incentives, employee efficiency improves.					
4.	Without the financial incentives, employees in this bank are not willing to increase the speed at which they work.					
5.	Employees in this bank do their works with no errors because of the financial incentives given to them.					
6.	This bank should continue giving its employees financial performance incentives in order to make the employees increase their efficiency.					

PART 3: Effect of Nonfinancial Performance Incentives (NFPI) on Employee Efficiency in DMB's in Dutsin-Ma LGA

S/N	Effect of NFPI on Employee Efficiency	1	2	3	4	5
1.	The nonfinancial performance incentives the employees in this bank enjoy, such as feedback to the employees, training, career development, recognition, employee participation and work environment are adequate.					
2.	Before the employees in this bank started enjoying the nonfinancial performance incentives, their efficiency, in terms of speed & accuracy, did not increase.					

3.	As soon as the employees in this bank started enjoying the nonfinancial performance incentives, their efficiency improved.					
4.	Without the nonfinancial performance incentives employees of this bank currently enjoy, they will not be willing to increase their efficiency.					
5.	Employees in this bank do their work with no errors due to the nonfinancial incentives they enjoy.					
6.	This bank should ensure that its employees continue to enjoy nonfinancial performance incentives in order to make the employees increase their efficiency.					